

Hochschule für Technik
und Wirtschaft Berlin

University of Applied Sciences

Comparative Evaluation of GeoSPARQL Implementations

Master Thesis

Name of the Study Programme

Master Professional IT Business and Digitalization

Faculty 3

from

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Date:

Berlin, 30.03.2025

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1. Introduction

The increasing use of geospatial data has necessitated the development of standardized methods for querying and managing geospatial data in a variety of domains including but not limited to, urban planning, environmental monitoring, transportation and especially geographic information systems (GIS). The GeoSPARQL standard, a specification for representing and querying geospatial data using and extending the SPARQL query language, is one of the most important developments in this area. GeoSPARQL provides a set of standardized functions and data types, designed to enable spatial queries of RDF data sets, making it an essential tool for working with geospatial information in the Semantic Web. As the geospatial data becomes more complex, the need for effective tools to manage and query this data is critical, especially for large datasets such as OpenStreetMap (OSM), which contain detailed information about geographic features around the world. OSM's extensive collection of geographic and feature data makes it a valuable resource for evaluating and benchmarking GeoSPARQL implementations. Despite the increasing adoption of GeoSPARQL, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that evaluate the performance and functionality of different GeoSPARQL implementations. This thesis aims to address this knowledge by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of popular GeoSPARQL implementations, Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB, using OSM data as the ground of testing.

1.1. Problem Statement

GeoSPARQL has become an increasingly utilized standard for the representation and retrieval of geospatial data within the RDF knowledge graphs. While numerous studies have been conducted to evaluate the GeoSPARQL implementations for standards compliance and query performance, these studies have mainly relied on synthetic datasets or simplified spatial data, designed and aimed to individually isolate spatial functions for testing purposes. However, the expanding adopting of volunteered geographic information (VGI) sources, such as OpenStreetMap (OSM), introduces a new non-trivial challenge for GeoSPARQL implementations.

OSM datasets are known to be imperfectly organized, inherently noisy and highly diverse from one another depending on regions and span multiple spatial scales. They range from individual cities to entire continents including one of the most prominent projects, OpenHistoricalMap. The effectiveness of GeoSPARQL implementations in handling such real-world spatial data at varying scales has not been the subject of a comprehensive evaluation. This study aims to address this gap by assessing the functionality and performance of GeoSPARQL-compliant triple stores using real-world OSM datasets. The evaluation will be conducted at the city (Berlin), country (Cambodia), and continental (Antarctica) scales.

The study's primary objective is to comprehensively assess the compliance of these systems with the fundamental principles of GeoSPARQL, while also investigating their capacity to effectively navigate the unique challenges imposed by OSM data. These challenges include unique and non-standard available geometries, complex spatial relationships, and real-world tagging schemes.

1.2. Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to conduct comprehensive comparative evaluation of GeoSPARQL implementations with a focus on functionality testing and benchmarking. The specific objectives of the research are as follows:

1.2.1. GeoSPARQL Implementations Evaluation with Functionality Testing

In order to achieve this objective, two steps must be taken. First, a comparison must be performed in GeoSPARQL support offered by the implementations. Second, real-world use cases must be built based on the supported features. The first step involves assessing the extent to which the implementations support the set of functions defined by the GeoSPARQL standards. These functions include, but are not limited to, spatial operators (e.g., `sfWithin`, `sfIntersects`), data properties (e.g., `geo:asWKT`), and data types (e.g., `wktLiteral`). The second step focuses on building use cases and developing GeoSPARQL queries based on those selected use cases using the actual OSM data. In Chapter 3, an investigative approach will be conducted on the methodology used to construct the use cases and queries. This investigation will address the fundamental question of how these components were integrated to facilitate the execution of functional testing procedures.

1.2.2. Benchmarking GeoSPARQL Implementations

Benchmarking in this thesis focuses on measuring and comparing the performance of different GeoSPARQL implementations under varied query loads. Indicators such as query execution time, resource consumption (e.g., memory and CPU usage), and scalability with large datasets will be measured and analyzed. The benchmarking process will evaluate the speed and accuracy of results when executing the same set of queries on different implementations, Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB. This will help identify how well the implementations handle OSM data which is categorized as challenging due to its extensive nature and diverse types of geographic features (e.g., roads, parks, buildings, natural features) under limited computational resources, a local setup environment in this case during the experiments, detailed in Chapter 4.

2. State of the Art

GeoSPARQL, an acronym for “A Geographic Query Language for RDF Data”, is a standard issued by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) ¹. The first version of GeoSPARQL, designated as GeoSPARQL 1.0, was released in 2012. This was followed by the most recent update, GeoSPARQL 1.1, which was published in 2024 ². The primary objective of this chapter is to introduce GeoSPARQL, and the additional concepts and properties that have been implemented in this latest version. At the time of writing this thesis, the future releases of GeoSPARQL are under development and in planning [1] with distinct updates to the current version as follows:

- 1.1 (current release): Extensions that are fully compatible with GeoSPARQL 1.0;
- 1.2: Contain necessary changes to GeoSPARQL 1.1 that needs to be accepted as an ISO-copublication ³.
- 1.3 (current draft) ⁴: An actual update to GeoSPARQL 1.1 with new features support on fully-featured 3D and GeoCoding literals support.
- 2.0: Future GeoSPARQL likely incompatible with GeoSPARQL 1.0.

GeoSPARQL is actually two things: an ontology for geo-spatial data and a query language [2]. The Ontology provides a standardized vocabulary for representing spatial data in RDF, including concepts like `geo:Feature`, `geo:Geometry`, and spatial relationships. The query language extends SPARQL with geospatial functions to perform spatial queries, such as `geof:distance()`, and `geof:sfIntersects()`.

2.1. GeoSPARQL - The Ontology

GeoSPARQL is primarily an ontology – a structured way to describe and organize geospatial data using RDF. GeoSPARQL follows a familiar way of handling spatial data. It defines two key concepts:

- Feature – A real-world object (e.g., a building, an airport, or a school).
- Geometry – The shape or location of that object, described using coordinates.

GeoSPARQL is designed to support both qualitative spatial reasoning systems and quantitative spatial computation systems. Qualitative spatial reasoning systems (e.g., those based on Region Connection Calculus) [3] typically do not explicitly use geometries. Instead, they evaluate spatial relationships between features, such as whether one region touches or contains another. Quantitative spatial computation systems, on the other hand, work with explicit geometries and perform calculations based on coordinates, such as checking if a point is within a polygon or measuring distances.

¹ <https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/geosparql/>

² <https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql11/document.html>

³ <https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql12/>

⁴ <https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql13/>

Listing: Example of `geo:hasGeometry` and `geo:hasDefaultGeometry`

```

PREFIX ex: <http://example.com/thing/>
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
ex:brisbane
  a geo:Feature ;
  rdfs:label "Brisbane Federal Electorate" ;
  geo:hasGeometry [
    a geo:Geometry ;
    geo:asWKT ""POLYGON ((
153.099932 -27.445258,
  ... ,
153.099932 -27.445258
  ))""^^geo:wktLiteral ;
  ] ;

```

In GeoSPARQL 1.1, two new additional classes `geo:FeatureCollection` and `geo:GeometryCollection` were added into the release. Geometry model collections can be done by using these two with RDF.

2.1.2. Data Types

The GeoSPARQL ontology specifies five data types which include: `WKTLiteral`, and `GMLLiteral` originally and `geoJSONLiteral`, `kmlLiteral`, and `dggsLiteral` following the new data properties addition in GeoSPARQL 1.1.

As the names imply, `WKTLiteral` and `GMLLiteral` are used in encoding geometries for `geo:asWKT` and `geo:asGML` data properties following the other three data types and their corresponding data properties. Here is an example⁸ of a geometry encoded as `WKTLiteral`.

Listing: Example of encoding geometries to `wktLiteral`

```

"http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84
POLYGON((21.5 18.5,23.5 18.5,
23.5 21,21.5 21,21.5 18.5))"
^^sf:wktLiteral.

```

2.1.3. Query Transformation Rules

Query transformation rules add another layer of flexibility for SPARQL queries. While the common possible case is directly comparing specific geometry objects, it is also useful to

⁸ <https://www.lirmm.fr/rod/slidesRoD04102018/RoD2018-tutorial.pdf>

check if two features have a certain relationship. For example, consider this question: “Is Reagan National Airport within Washington, DC?” [4] Even though the airport is often referred to a Washington, DC airport, it is actually located in Virginia, across the Potomac River. The following listing shows an example of a query that defines a relationship between two `geo:Feature` objects, `ex:DCA` and `ex:WashingtonDC` before and after the rewrite.

Listing: Example of using rewrite for `ex:DCA` and `ex:WashingtonDC`

```
#Before
ASK {
  ex:DCA a geo:Feature;
  geo:sfWithin ex:WashingtonDC .
  ex:WashingtonDC a geo:Feature .
}

#After
ASK {
  ex:DCA a geo:Feature;
  geo:defaultGeometry ?g1 .
  ex:WashingtonDC a geo:Feature ;
  geo:defaultGeometry ?g2 .
  ?g1 geo:sfWithin ?g2 .
}
```

In GeoSPARQL, topological relationships between features and geometries are handled using the `geo:defaultGeometry` along with query rewrite rules. As shown in the example above, instead of directly checking if `ex:DCA` is within `ex:WashingtonDC` feature that does not contain any geometry data using `geo:sfWithin` function – which should apply to geometries and not features, we first retrieve their geometries: `?g1` and `?g2` for both features and now it is possible to compare `?g1 geo:sfWithin ?g2` .

2.1.4. Data Properties

GeoSPARQL provides two standard formats for representing geometry literals: Well-Known Text (WKT) ⁹and Geographic Markup Language (GML) ¹⁰. In GeoSPARQL ontology, these are represented using the two data properties below:

- `geo:asWKT` – Store geometries of features in WKT format (e.g., `:CityA geo:asWKT "Point(-77.03653 38.897676)"^^geo:wktLiteral.`)
- `geo:asGML` – Store geometries in GML format following XML-based syntax

⁹ WKT: Text markup language for representing vector geometry objects - <https://w.wiki/4Aj8>

¹⁰ GML: XML grammar defined by OGC to express geographical features - <https://w.wiki/D6vH>

In addition to two above data properties, three properties for geometry representation were added into GeoSPARQL 1.1: `geo:asGeoJSON`, and `geo:asKML`, `geo:asDGGs`.

2.2. GeoSPARQL – The Query Language

In previous section, GeoSPARQL as an ontology was discussed. In this section, the second part of GeoSPARQL, the query language will be discussed. GeoSPARQL extends SPARQL language providing the standard to query and manipulate spatial data in triple stores. GeoSPARQL leverages SPARQL by adding several sets of functions to be used within `SELECT` and `FILTER` statements. Those functions are usually defined in the document with the abbreviation prefix of `geof:` with URI: `http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/`.

The functions are categorized into two main groups: Non-topological and Topological. While Non-topological functions perform operations that do not involve spatial relationships, such as geometry calculations and transformations, the latter assess spatial relationships between geometries. Topological functions further categorize into three subcategories: Simple Features, Egenhofer and RCC8. The following sections list some of commonly used functions by groups and which they could be used throughout the queries developed and used for the thesis.

2.2.1. Non-topological Functions ¹¹

<code>geof:distance</code>	computes shortest distance between two geometries.
<code>geof:buffer</code>	returns a geometric object representing all points whose distance from geometry is less than or equal to the specified radius.
<code>geof:convexHull</code>	returns a geometric object representing all points in the convex hull of the argument.
<code>geof:intersection</code>	returns all points that intersect two geometries.
<code>geof:union</code>	returns all points in the union of two geometries.
<code>geof:difference</code>	returns all points in the set of difference between two geometries.
<code>geof:symDifference</code>	returns all points in the set of symmetric difference between two geometries.
<code>geof:envelop</code>	returns the closure of the boundary of the specified geometry.
<code>geof:boundary</code>	returns the closure of the boundary of the specified geometry.
<code>geof:getsrid</code>	returns the SRS ¹² URI for the specified geometry.
<code>geof:transform*</code>	transforms a geometry literal into a different coordinate system defined by the <code>srsIRI</code> parameter.
<code>geof:relate</code>	evaluates if specified geometries matches to the pattern.

¹¹ * = New functions provided in GeoSPARQL 1.1.

¹² SRS = Spatial Reference System

<code>geof:geometry*</code>	given a Geometry literal composed by multiple instances, returns the individual at the given index.
<code>geof:numGeometries*</code>	given a Geometry literal composed by multiple individuals, returns the its total number of individuals.

GeoSPARQL 1.1. also introduced six new aggregate functions for computation: `geof:aggBoundingBox`, `geof:BoundingBox`, `geof:Centroid`, `geof:ConcaveHull`, `geof:ConvexHull`, and `geof:aggUnion`. The following examples from “cambridgesemantics”¹³ show how these functions are used in queries.

Listing: Example of using intersection

```
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:intersection(?x,?y) as ?intersection)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('LINESTRING (8 7, 7 8)' 'LINESTRING (2 0, 2 3)')
    ('LINESTRING (0 2, 0 0, 2 0)' 'LINESTRING (0 3, 0 1, 1 0, 3 0)')
  }
}
```

Listing: Example of using union

```
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:union(?x,?y) as ?union)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>LINESTRING (8 7, 7
8)'^^geo:wktLiteral '<gml:LineString gml:id="p21"
srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326"><gml:coordinates>2,0
2,3</gml:coordinates></gml:LineString>'^^geo:gmlLiteral)
    ('LINESTRING (0 2, 0 0, 2 0)'^^geo:wktLiteral 'LINESTRING (0 3, 0 1, 1 0,
3 0)'^^geo:wktLiteral)
  }
}
```

¹³ <https://docs.cambridgesemantics.com/graphlakehouse/v3.2/userdoc/geosparql-sparql.htm#NonTopologicalFunctions>

2.2.2. Simple Features

GeoSPARQL provides a set of Simple Feature Family relation functions for checking how two geometries overlap using DE-9IM¹⁴ patterns. They are used for assessing general-purpose spatial relationships that aligned with OGC Simple Features and applied to all geometry types (Points, lines, polygons). All the functions follow the same structure where two geometries are provided as input and a Boolean value of `true` or `false` is returned as output.

<code>sfEquals</code>	checks whether geometries are equal.
<code>sfDisjoint</code>	checks whether geometries are disjoint.
<code>sfIntersects</code>	checks whether geometries intersect.
<code>sfTouches</code>	checks whether geometries touch.
<code>sfCrosses</code>	checks whether the first geometry spatially crosses the second geometry.
<code>sfWithin</code>	checks whether the first geometry spatially is within the second geometry.
<code>sfContains</code>	checks whether the first geometry contains the second geometry.
<code>sfOverlaps</code>	checks whether the first geometry spatially overlaps the second geometry.

The following examples of queries from “cambridgesemantics”¹⁵ show the Simple Features functions are actually used.

Listing: Example of using `sfEquals`

```

PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:sfEquals(?x,?y) as ?is_equal)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('Point (2 3)' 'Point (2 3)')
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4
1))' ^^geo:wktLiteral '<gml:Point gml:id="p21"
srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326">
<gml:coordinates>2,3</gml:coordinates></gml:Point>' ^^geo:gmlLiteral)
  }
}

```

¹⁴ Dimensionally Extended 9-Intersection Model – a topological model and a standard used to describe the spatial relations of two regions <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DE-9IM>

¹⁵ <https://docs.cambridgesemantics.com/graphlakehouse/v3.2/userdoc/geosparql-sparql.htm#simple-feature>

Listing: Example of using sfCrosses

```

PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:sfCrosses(?x,?y) as ?crosses)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('LINESTRING (2 0, 2 3)' 'POLYGON ((30 10 , 40 40, 20 40, 10 20, 30 10))')
    ('<gml:LineString gml:id="p21"
srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326"><gml:coordinates>2,0
2,3</gml:coordinates></gml:LineString>'^^geo:gmlLiteral
'<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>POLYGON ((1 1 , 1 4, 4 4, 4
1))'^^geo:wktLiteral)
  }
}

```

2.2.3. Egenhofer

The Egenhofer Family relation functions are used for fine-grained analysis of boundary/interior interactions based on the DE-9IM. The functions are generally applied to points, lines and polygons. The functions take the same input and returns the same output to the previously categorized group of functions. The following examples of queries also obtained from “cambridgesemantics”¹⁶ show the Simple Egenhofer functions are actually used.

ehEquals	checks whether geometries are equal.
ehDisjoint	checks whether geometries are disjoint.
ehMeet	checks whether geometries meet.
ehOverlap	checks whether geometries overlap.
ehCovers	checks whether the first geometry spatially covers the second geometry.
ehCoveredBy	checks whether the first geometry is covered by the second geometry.
ehInside	checks whether the first geometry is inside the second geometry.
ehContains	checks whether the first geometry spatially is contained in the second geometry.

2.2.4. RCC8

The last category of Topological group functions is RCC8 Family functions where they are used for logical region-based reasoning following the same structure of input and output to The Simple Feature functions. This group of functions apply only to areas (2D regions).

¹⁶ <https://docs.cambridgesemantics.com/graphlakehouse/v3.2/userdoc/geosparql-sparql.htm#egenhofer-family>

rcc8eq	checks whether geometries are equal.
rcc8dc	checks whether geometries are disjoint.
rcc8ec	checks whether geometries are externally connected.
rcc8po	checks whether geometries overlap.
rcc8tpp	checks whether one geometry is a tangential proper part of another geometry.
rcc8tppi	checks whether one geometry is a tangential proper part inverse of another geometry.
rcc8nttp	checks whether one geometry is a non-tangential proper part of another geometry.
rcc8nttpi	checks whether one geometry is a non-tangential proper part inverse of another geometry.

The last set of examples queries were also obtained from “cambridgesemantics”¹⁷ showing how the RCC8 Family functions are actually used.

Listing: Example of using rcc8dc

```
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:rcc8dc(?x,?y) as ?is_dc)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' 'POLYGON ((11 11, 11 14, 14 14, 14 11))')
    ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' ^^geo:wktLiteral 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' ^^geo:wktLiteral)
  }
}
```

Listing: Example of using rcc8tppi

```
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:rcc8tppi(?x,?y) as ?is_tppi)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('POLYGON ((2 2, 5 2, 5 4, 2 4))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 6, 4 1, 4 6))')
    ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))')
  }
}
```

¹⁷ <https://docs.cambridgesemantics.com/graphlakehouse/v3.2/userdoc/geosparql-sparql.htm#rcc8-family>

Listing: Example of using rcc8ntpp

```

PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
SELECT (geof:rcc8ntpp(?x,?y) as ?is_ntpp)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y) {
    ('POLYGON ((2 2, 5 2, 5 4, 2 4))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 6, 4 1, 4 6))')
    ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))')
  }
}

```

2.3. GeoSPARQL Implementations

A GeoSPARQL implementation is primarily a SPARQL engine that provides GeoSPARQL support. It enables the features such as: storing, querying, and providing reasoning over RDF data format. As previously discussed in section 2.2, GeoSPARQL extends SPARQL, the query language with added capabilities such as geometry representation, spatial relationships, and spatial functions. Since GeoSPARQL implementations are commonly and originally SPARQL engines, another feature is also found in the programs, SPARQL endpoint where every query is available for API calls. This specific feature will be used as a part of benchmarking process which will later be detailed in chapter 3. To summarize, key characteristics and features of a GeoSPARQL implementation are as follows:

- Geospatial Data Storage – RDF triples could include geospatial information in WKT (Well-Known Text) or GML (Geography Markup Language) formats.
- Spatial Querying – Allows spatial queries using SPARQL, such as distance computation between locations and points finding within a polygon.
- Geospatial Reasoning – Supports topological relationships like intersects, within, contains, allowing inference over spatial data.

2.4. Apache Jena Fuseki

Apache Jena, formerly known as Jena before Apache integrated it into The Apache Software Foundation in April 2012, is an open-source Semantic Web framework for Java. Similarly functioning as a SPARQL engine, it provides an API for data extraction from and to write RDF graphs. Jena provides support for various formats of serialization including ¹⁸: a relational database, RDF/XML, Turtle, TriG, Notation 3, and JSON-LD.

Apache Jena Fuseki, on the other hand is the Jena SPARQL server that provides interface that makes querying and managing triples and RDF easier and more convenient.

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Apache_Jena

However, Apache Jena Fuseki does not provide GeoSPARQL support by default. `jena-fuseki-geosparql` therefore, is made available for the purpose. It can be accessed as an embedded server using Maven as well as the binary format, which can be downloaded from the Maven central repository¹⁹. The latter option was actually used in this thesis for running the program. Since `jena-fuseki-geosparql` does not come with GUI, there is a certain way that it could be run using Apache Jena Fuseki as an UI wrapper. It is noted in the documentation that GUI is currently in development plan as future work, assisting users when querying the data. Next section shows exactly the way to do it and get the server up and running with the GUI.

2.4.1. Licensing

As previously mentioned, Apache Jena Fuseki is an open-source project. Based on the documentation, it is claimed that the implementation follows 1.0 GeoSPARQL standard. The implementation is pure Java and does not require any set-up or configuration of any third-party relational databases and geospatial extension. Although being an open-source implementation, it is said to apply and comply with six Conformance Classes as described in the GeoSPARQL standard. Those six Conformance Classes include: Core, Topology Vocabulary, Geometry Extension, RDFS Entailment Extension, Query Rewrite Extension. Additionally, the three spatial relation families: Simple Feature, Egenhofer and RCC8 are also supported.

2.4.2. Installation

The binary distribution of the Fuseki server can be obtained directly from the downloads site²⁰ and more options are available on the page²¹. Meanwhile, the self-contained JAR file of `jena-fuseki-geosparql` must also be downloaded²². Following the download of these files, the JAR file of `jena-fuseki-geosparql` must be placed in the `/lib` directory of the Apache Jena Fuseki directory. The following command starts the Apache Jena Fuseki with GeoSPARQL support, specifying the classpath `-cp` to include all the jar files in the `/lib` directory.

Listing: Command for running Apache Jena Fuseki

```
java -cp "fuseki-server.jar:lib/*" org.apache.jena.fuseki.cmd.FusekiCmd --config run/config.ttl --debug
```

2.5. Ontotext GraphDB

Ontotext GraphDB, shortened as GraphDB later in the rest of the thesis content, developed and provided by Ontotext company, is a highly efficient, scalable and robust graph database

¹⁹ <https://repo1.maven.org/maven2/org/apache/jena/jena-fuseki-geosparql/>

²⁰ <https://dlcdn.apache.org/jena/binaries/apache-jena-fuseki-5.3.0.zip>

²¹ <https://jena.apache.org/download/index.cgi>

²² <https://repo1.maven.org/maven2/org/apache/jena/jena-fuseki-geosparql/>

with RDF and SPARQL support ²³. It implements the RDF4J ²⁴ framework interfaces, the W3C SPARQL Protocol specification. Serialization support is also available in all RDF formats. Unlike Apache Jena Fuseki, GeoSPARQL feature on GraphDB could easily be turned on via the web-based administration portal and actually enabled by default. Section 2.5.2 shows the interface on how it could be turned on. In the next section, licensing of GraphDB is detailed and differences between the licenses will be listed.

2.5.1. Licensing

GraphDB offers two kinds of licenses: GraphDB Free and GraphDB Enterprise. While both types give the same common features such as:

- Fully compliant with RDF 1.1 and SPARQL 1.1, with RDF-Star and SPARQL-Star extensions.
- Fully compliant reasoning for the standard rulesets RDFS, OWL 2 RL and QL.
- 100% compatible with the RDF4J framework

GraphDB Enterprise, however, provides additional features like Lucene connector for full-text search, Solr connector for full-text search, Elasticsearch connector and Kafka connector for downstream synchronization. Workbench or web-based interface is also available for both types for managing repositories, data, user accounts and access roles. It is also important to note that with GraphDB Free which is actually used in the thesis for the experiments process, comes with single-core license only. The next section shows how to obtain the program and set it up.

2.5.2. Installation

GraphDB can only be obtained by making a request on the Ontotext page ²⁵. Once the request is made, users will receive an email containing the links to download the program. GraphDB is available in a variety of installation options, including desktop, standalone, and cloud setups on Azure and AWS. In this thesis, the standalone server version was selected due to the fact that certain command options are only available in this edition. The following command is used to start the engine with allocation of maximum heap size of 10GB. GeoSPARQL is turned on by default with GraphDB as shown in the following figure.

Listing: Command for running GraphDB

```
→ graphdb-10.8.3 ./bin/graphdb -Xmx10g
```


Figure 2: GeoSPARQL plugin turned on by default on GraphDB (Setup -> Plugins)

²³ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/10.8/index.html>

²⁴ <https://rdf4j.org>

²⁵ <https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/>

2.6. Getting Started with GeoSPARQL

One of the prominent features provided by GraphDB documentation is a sample RDF document with a set of GeoSPARQL example queries, giving an overview and quick insight to users on how the program supports GeoSPARQL. Below is a list of four SELECT queries on geographic data. Sample dataset `geosparql-example.rdf`²⁶ can be downloaded and imported into a repository on GraphDB with GeoSPARQL plugin enabled as shown in the section 2.5.2. The RDF dataset defines the following figure for spatial objects.

Figure 3: Spatial objects representing `geosparql-example.rdf`

Listing: Prefixes used in the example queries

```
PREFIX my: <http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#>
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
PREFIX uom: <http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/OGC/1.0/>
```

2.6.1.1. Example 1

Find all features that feature `my:A` contains, where spatial calculations are based on `my:hasExactGeometry`.

Listing: Example 1 of GeoSPARQL query from GraphDB

```
SELECT ?f
WHERE {
  my:A my:hasExactGeometry ?aGeom .
  ?aGeom geo:asWKT ?aWKT .
  ?f my:hasExactGeometry ?fGeom .
```

²⁶ https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/10.8/_downloads/d10860b42c7c39e3d05ef397f5756ca1/geosparql-example.rdf

```

    ?fGeom geo:asWKT ?fWKT .
  FILTER (geof:sfContains(?aWKT, ?fWKT) && !sameTerm(?aGeom, ?fGeom))
}

```

Listing: Result of Example 1 tested on GraphDB

```

f
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#B
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#F

```

2.6.1.2. Example 2

Find all features that are within a transient bounding box geometry, where spatial calculations are based on `my:hasPointGeometry`.

Listing: Example 2 of GeoSPARQL query from GraphDB

```

SELECT ?f
WHERE {
  ?f my:hasPointGeometry ?fGeom .
  ?fGeom geo:asWKT ?fWKT .
  FILTER (geof:sfWithin(?fWKT, '''
    <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84>
    Polygon ((-83.4 34.0, -83.1 34.0,
              -83.1 34.2, -83.4 34.2,
              -83.4 34.0))
    '''^^geo:wktLiteral))
}

```

Listing: Result of Example 2 tested on GraphDB

```

f
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#D

```

2.6.1.3. Example 3

Find all features that touch the union of feature `my:A` and feature `my:D`, where computations are based on `my:hasExactGeometry`.

Listing: Example 3 of GeoSPARQL query from GraphDB

```

SELECT ?f
WHERE {
  ?f my:hasExactGeometry ?fGeom .
  ?fGeom geo:asWKT ?fWKT .
  my:A my:hasExactGeometry ?aGeom .
}

```

```

?aGeom geo:asWKT ?aWKT .
my:D my:hasExactGeometry ?dGeom .
?dGeom geo:asWKT ?dWKT .
FILTER (geof:sfTouches(?fWKT, geof:union(?aWKT, ?dWKT)))
}

```

Listing: Result of Example 3 tested on GraphDB

```

f
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#C

```

2.6.1.4. Example 4

Find the 3 closest features to feature my:C, where computations are based on my:hasExactGeometry.

Listing: Example 4 of GeoSPARQL query from GraphDB

```

SELECT ?f
WHERE {
  my:C my:hasExactGeometry ?cGeom .
  ?cGeom geo:asWKT ?cWKT .
  ?f my:hasExactGeometry ?fGeom .
  ?fGeom geo:asWKT ?fWKT .
  FILTER (?fGeom != ?cGeom)
}
ORDER BY ASC(geof:distance(?cWKT, ?fWKT, uom:metre))
LIMIT 3

```

Listing: Result of Example 4 tested on GraphDB

```

f
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#A
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#E
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#D

```

3. Methodology

The thesis is focused on two primary objectives: functionality testing and benchmarking. To accomplish these objectives, the use of GeoSPARQL implementations, also known as “triple stores”²⁷, is necessary. This chapter provides a detailed examination of the process of comparison and evaluation for GeoSPARQL implementations.

Although many triple stores have adopted the standard and started providing support for GeoSPARQL in respective programs, the functionality, usability and performance may vary across the programs due to their own spatial indexing strategies and architectural differences. To date, a considerable number of papers and studies have been conducted to either assess and focus solely on individual implementation or to conduct benchmarking against the expected results of the GeoSPARQL standards using static simplified and synthetic datasets only.

The objective of this therefore is to address the aforementioned gap by comparing and evaluating functionality and benchmarking using different use cases across various sized datasets on two selected implementations: Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB. An overview of the methodology carried out for achieving each objective is discussed in the following sections.

3.1. Selection of GeoSPARQL Implementations

Both Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB are commonly used and chosen for RDF triplestores management and their GeoSPARQL support. In fact, a Journal Article “A GeoSPARQL Compliance Benchmark” showed that GeoSPARQL Jena Fuseki and GraphDB topped the results for complying with the requirements set out by GeoSPARQL standard, scoring 82.75% and 69.75% [5] respectively. While Apache Jena Fuseki is open-source, GraphDB also provides the freeware version along with their enterprise edition. Therefore, choosing these two implementations provides insights into trade-offs between free and paid solutions.

Although they both support GeoSPARQL, their distinct indexing strategies may impact performance and scalabilities differently. To investigate the differences, functionality and benchmarking will be conducted to assess their support in handling queries and their claim in adhering to GeoSPARQL standards compliance.

This choice of selection aims to provide insights into capabilities and limitations of the chosen implementations.

²⁷ Triple stores: purpose-built databases for storing and retrieving triples using semantic queries - <https://w.wiki/D7Yi>

3.2. Datasets Selection

In order to conduct functionality testing and perform benchmarking, datasets containing proper geospatial data are required. Fortunately, there are a few sites that provide OpenStreetMap (OSM) datasets with RDF extracts; geofabrik²⁸ and osm2rdf²⁹ are selected in the thesis. The former provides daily updated dataset files in `.osm.pbf` and `.shp.zip` formats of sub-regions and countries followed by cities (where available) in every continent while the latter provides weekly updated zipped triples in Turtle format `.ttl.bz2` files for entire planet OSM data as well as extracts for individual continents and countries. There are three datasets obtained for use in this thesis, including:

- City-level: Berlin named `berlin-latest-osm.pbf`
- Country-level: Cambodia named `khm-osm.ttl.bz2`
- Continent-level: Antarctica named `ata-osm.ttl.bz2`

Listing: Datasets obtained from geofabrik and osm2rdf sites

dataset	type	size	source
<code>berlin-latest.osm.pbf</code>	city	88.1 MB	geofabrik
<code>khm.osm.ttl.bz2</code>	country	234 MB	osm2rdf
<code>ata.osm.ttl.bz2</code>	continent	86.7 MB	osm2rdf

3.3. Datasets Preparation

After obtaining the datasets, conversion and unzipping processes to RDF format files are necessary for the `berlin-latest.osm.pbf` and the other two datasets, respectively. Many tools are available to serve the conversion purpose. However, after researching and testing on so many programs, `osm2rdf`, [6] first introduced as `osm2ttl` and provided by the University of Freiburg³⁰ was determined to be the easiest and most efficient to set up and process. The following command is used to build the Docker image following the cloning of the repository from `osm2rdf`'s github repository.

Listing: Docker command for building `osm2rdf`

```
docker build -t osm2rdf
```

The following listing shows the command used for converting the “Berlin” dataset to RDF compatible for the GeoSPARQL implementations in `.ttl` format file.

²⁸ <https://download.geofabrik.de/>

²⁹ <https://osm2rdf.cs.uni-freiburg.de/>

³⁰ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/osm2rdf>

Listing: Docker command for converting Berlin dataset to .ttl format

```
docker run --rm -v `pwd`/input:/input/ -v `pwd`/output:/output/ -v
`pwd`/scratch:/scratch/ -it osm2rdf ./input/berlin-latest.osm.pbf -o
/output/berlin-latest.osm.ttl -t /scratch/
```

Meanwhile, since khm and ata datasets are already available in zipped turtle format files, all was needed to be done is unzipping the files.

Listing: Details of datasets after conversion and unzipping processes

dataset	type	new size	source
berlin-latest.osm.pbf	city	23.56 GB	geofabrik
khm.osm.ttl.bz2	country	2.56 GB	osm2rdf
ata.osm.ttl.bz2	continent	513.7 MB	osm2rdf

3.4. Functionality Testing on Static Example Queries

In addition to the functionality testing with examples provided exclusively by GraphDB in section 2.6 as an initial functionality testing phase, there are many other GeoSPARQL functions and spatial relations that shall also be tested in order to conduct the functionality testing between chosen implementations and make a comparison.

However, instead of testing the functionality using the sample RDF document provided by either of the implementations, all sets of examples from Cambridgesemantics³¹ will be used. This decision is motivated by the observation that, among the examples provided by GraphDB (see Section 2.6.1.4), example 4 shows a different result when executed on Apache Jena Fuseki.

Listing: Result of Example 4 tested on Apache Jena Fuseki

```
f
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#A
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#B
http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#D
```

Furthermore, the use of example queries in the testing of GeoSPARQL functions from Cambridgesemantics reflects the actual functionality observed in both implementations. For instance, geof:distance returned no results on Apache Jena Fuseki (also see Section 4.4 for further investigation), while GraphDB returned the expected results. The results of this GeoSPARQL functionality testing will be presented and discussed in Chapter 5. During the testing phase on GeoSPARQL functions, however, numerous samples provided by Cambridgesemantics failed due to syntax and incomplete query structure. Therefore, many of the examples were corrected to accommodate this failure. The following figures show an example of such failure and the result after making query adjustment and syntax correction.

³¹ <https://docs.cambridgesemantics.com/graphlakehouse/v3.2/userdoc/geosparql-sparql.htm#GeoSPARQLFunctions>

```

1 PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
2 SELECT (geof:rcc8ec(?x,?y) as ?is_ec)
3 WHERE {
4 VALUES (?x ?y) {
5 ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' 'POLYGON ((4 1, 6 1, 6 4, 4 4))')
6 ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))')
7 }
8 }

```

400: Error
Syntax error in query: Points of LinearRing do not form a closed linestring

Query took 0.1s, moments ago.

Figure 4: Query results of `geof:rcc8ec` from *Cambridgesemantics* on *GraphDB*

```

1 PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
2 SELECT (geof:rcc8ec(?x,?y) as ?is_ec)
3 WHERE {
4 VALUES (?x ?y) {
5 ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1, 1 1))' 'POLYGON ((4 1, 6 1, 6 4, 4 4, 4 1))')
6 ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1, 1 1))' 'POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1, 1 1))')
7 }
8 }

```

Table | Raw response | Pivot Table | Google Chart

Filter query results | Compact view Hide row numbers | Showing results from 0 to 2 of 2. Query took 0.1s, moments ago.

	is_ec
1	"true" <i>**xsd:boolean</i>
2	"false" <i>**xsd:boolean</i>

Figure 5: Query results of `geof:rcc8ec` after query modification on *GraphDB*

3.5. Use Case Development Based on GeoSPARQL Functionality

In order to comprehensively and effectively evaluate the functionality of GeoSPARQL implementations, a set of six designed use cases has been selected corresponding to the datasets obtained and readily processed in section 3.2 and section 3.3 respectively. Two use cases have been designed and assigned for each dataset with different relevant real-world scenarios and questions. The six use cases that follow were developed in consideration of the functions that have demonstrated successful operation in the context of spatial relations. This development is founded on the initial functionality testing that was conducted utilizing the sample RDF document that was provided by *GraphDB* documented in section 2.5 followed by the documented capabilities in the previous section. They are aimed at testing various aspects of GeoSPARQL compliance, including spatial functions, query complexity and data retrieval accuracy. They also serve as practical scenarios that reflect real-world geospatial queries while ensuring that functionality is mainly tested and adhered to the GeoSPARQL standard.

3.5.1. Use Cases Selection

The selection of use cases is built upon the characteristics of the datasets utilized in this thesis, which include the geospatial data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) for different sized regions. Each dataset represents a different geographical area and vast amount of data inputs, which were chosen together to provide diversity in query complexity and data structure. The use cases were formulated to cover a wide range of GeoSPARQL functions, ensuring that each implementation is tested against both fundamental and advanced spatial queries. While the main purpose of using and building use cases to evaluate functionality of the implementations is to ensure and measure effectiveness in using GeoSPARQL to answer potential real-world scenario questions based on the actual datasets followed by varied available entities and types of data depending on regions and its updates, the following also reflect the criteria for choosing the use cases:

- **Relevance** to real-world scenarios and actual information made available on each dataset.
- **Coverage of diverse GeoSPARQL functions** including the use of spatial relationships (e.g., `geof:sfWithin`, `geof:sfIntersects`) and distance filtering.
- **Data complexity** including both point-based (e.g., shops, restaurants) and polygon-based (e.g., buildings) in the datasets in order to evaluate how the implementations handle different spatial data types.
- **Performance variability** where some queries are computationally simple (e.g., finding nearby points of interest with `geof:distance`) and some others are rather complex (e.g., aggregating spatial regions)

The following six use cases have been selected for evaluating the functionality testing against the actual datasets:

1. Top 10 places to visit from Galeria Alexanderplatz.
2. Closest parks (within 500m) to museums.
3. Get the number of attractions for each province in Cambodia.
4. Find coffee shops within or intersects with Russian Market Phnom Penh of 750m.
5. Get research stations in Antarctica.
6. Get research stations close to volcanoes less than 1km.

3.5.2. Queries Development

Given that the thesis uses OSM data mainly for the development of building use cases and queries, it is essential to understand the OSM data structure and tagging schemes. Prior to the possibility of constructing queries for each case, a method of data exploration involving searching for all the subjects and objects using predicates such as: `osmkey` and `osmkey:amenity`.

Listing: Example query retrieving osmkey tags for examination

```

PREFIX osmkey: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:>
PREFIX osm: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?p WHERE {
  ?s ?p ?o
  FILTER (
    STRSTARTS(STR(?p), STR(osmkey:))
  )
}

```

Listing: Sample results of osmkey tags from ata dataset

```

p
https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:addr:postcode
https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:alt_name
https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:capacity:persons

```

Listing: Example query retrieving osmkey:amenity key for examination

```

PREFIX osmkey: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:>
SELECT DISTINCT ?amenity
WHERE {
  ?feature osmkey:amenity ?amenity ;
}
ORDER BY ?amenity

```

Listing: Sample results of osmkey:amenity key from ata dataset

```

atm
bank
bar
cafe

```

Moreover, in GraphDB, each result links to a detail page depending on the availability of the data, enabling further debugging and investigation. This facilitated more rapid and effective development of queries. For example, the following figure lists all the predicates of osm:way with ID: 190942449.

	subject	predicate	object	context
1	osm:way/190942449	geo:hasCentroid	osm2rdfgeom:osm_area_centroid_381884898	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
2	osm:way/190942449	geo:hasGeometry	osm2rdfgeom:osm_wayarea_190942449	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
3	osm:way/190942449	ogc:sfIntersects	osmrel:15543171	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
4	osm:way/190942449	ogc:sfIntersects	osmrel:17349155	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
5	osm:way/190942449	ogc:sfIntersects	osmrel:1844217	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
6	osm:way/190942449	rdf:type	osm:way	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
7	osm:way/190942449	osm2rdf.area	*0.000000077261**xsd:double	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
8	osm:way/190942449	osm2rdf.facts	*6**xsd:integer	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
9	osm:way/190942449	osm2rdf.length	*0.001843**xsd:double	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit
10	osm:way/190942449	osm2rdfgeom:convex_hull	*POLYGON((166.6614744 - 77.8302672,166.6623068 - 77.8301932,166.6614744 - 77.8302672))* **http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#wktLiteral*	http://www.ontotext.com/explicit

Figure 6: Details of osm:way 190942449 on GraphDB

Each use case involves with writing and refining the GeoSPARQL queries that leverage different spatial functions. Below is a detailed description of each use case followed by its query development process.

Listing: Prefixes used in the following use case queries

```
PREFIX osmkey: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX uom: <http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/OGC/1.0/>
PREFIX osm2rdfgeom: <https://osm2rdf.cs.uni-freiburg.de/rdf/geom#>
```

3.5.2.1. Use Case # 1

Objective

Determine the top 10 tourist attractions from Galeria in Alexanderplatz square as the starting point.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geof:distance` – Calculates distance between Galeria and attraction coordinates.

Query development

1. Sets Galeria coordinates in Alexanderplatz as the starting point using `BIND` and serialize it to WKT format using `geo:wktLiteral`.
 2. Retrieves all attractions with their geometries using `osmkey:tourism` and `geo:hasGeometry` and get the coordinates in WKT format using `geo:asWKT`.
 3. Optionally retrieves attraction names and operators using `osmkey:name` and `osmkey:operator`.
 4. Filters attraction types to ("viewpoint", "museum", "zoo", "tower_viewer", "attraction", "gallery", "arts_center") only.
 5. Filters attractions less than or equal to 5km from Galeria.
 6. Sort by the distances in ascending order with limit 10 places.
-

Listing: Query for Use Case #1

```
# top 10 places to visit starting with Galeria as starting point
SELECT ?attraction (COALESCE(?attrName, ?operator) AS ?name_operator) ?type
?distance
WHERE {
  # BIND galeria in alexanderplatz as starting point
  BIND("POINT(13.411675 52.522415)"^^geo:wktLiteral AS ?galeria )

  # Get attractions with key:tourism
  ?attraction osmkey:tourism ?type ;
    geo:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geo:asWKT ?attractionWKT .

  OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:name ?attrName }
  OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:operator ?operator }

  FILTER(?type IN("viewpoint", "museum", "zoo", "tower_viewer", "attraction",
"gallery", "arts_center"))

  BIND(round(geof:distance(?galeria, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre)) AS ?distance)
  FILTER(?distance <=5000)
}
ORDER BY ?distance
LIMIT 10
```

Expected results

A list of attractions, attraction names preferred over operators, the type of attraction and the distance between the attraction and Galeria.

3.5.2.2. Use Case # 2

Objective

Find the nearest parks to each museum in Berlin by computing the shortest distance between the museum's centroid and the park's centroid.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geo:hasGeometry` – Retrieves spatial representations of entities.
 - `geo:hasCentroid` – Extracts the centroid of a polygon.
 - `geo:asWKT` – Retrieves the geometries in WKT.
 - `geof:distance` – Calculates distances between museums and parks in meter unit.
-

Query development

1. Retrieves museums using `osmkey:tourism` "museum", their geometries with `geo:hasGeometry` together with the geometries using `geo:asWKT`.
 2. Optionally retrieves `geo:asWKT` value of the museum if `geo:hasCentroid` exists.
 3. Uses `?museumWKT` instead if `?museumCentroidWKT` does not exist and assign it to `?museumPoint`.
 4. Retrieves parks using `osmkey:leisure` "park", their geometries with `geo:hasGeometry` together with the geometries using `geo:asWKT`.
 5. Optionally retrieves `geo:asWKT` value of the park if `geo:hasCentroid` exists.
 6. Uses `?parkWKT` instead if `?parkCentroidWKT` does not exist and assign it to `?parkPoint`.
 7. Computes distances between `?museumPoint` and `?parkPoint` in metre measurement unit.
 8. Filters the distances shorter than 500m from the museums.
 9. Orders the results by the museums, then parks in ascending order.
 10. Limits the results to 10 only.
-

Listing: Query for Use Case #2

```
# get the closest parks (within 500m) to museums, limit to 10
SELECT DISTINCT ?museum ?museumName ?parkName ?distance
WHERE {
  # Get museums
  ?museum osmkey:tourism "museum" ;
          osmkey:name ?museumName ;
          geo:hasGeometry ?museumGeom .
  ?museumGeom geo:asWKT ?museumWKT .
  OPTIONAL {
```

```

    ?museum geo:hasCentroid ?museumCentroid .
    ?museumCentroid geo:asWKT ?museumCentroidWKT .
  }
  # If no centroid, use the main geometry
  BIND(COALESCE(?museumCentroidWKT, ?museumWKT) AS ?museumPoint)

  # Get parks
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park" ;
    osmkey:name ?parkName ;
    geo:hasGeometry ?parkGeom .
  ?parkGeom geo:asWKT ?parkWKT .
  OPTIONAL {
    ?park geo:hasCentroid ?parkCentroid .
    ?parkCentroid geo:asWKT ?parkCentroidWKT .
  }
  # If no centroid, use the main geometry
  BIND(COALESCE(?parkCentroidWKT, ?parkWKT) AS ?parkPoint)
  # Compute distance between museum and park
  BIND(geof:distance(?museumPoint, ?parkPoint, uom:metre) AS ?distance)
  FILTER(?distance < 500)
}
ORDER BY ?museumName ?distance
LIMIT 10

```

Expected results

A list of museums and the names, closest park names, and the distance between them.

3.5.2.3. Use Case # 3

Objective

Retrieves the number of historical sites for each province in Cambodia by calculating the distances between the sites and provinces within 50km from one another.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geo:hasGeometry` – Retrieves spatial representations of historical sites.
 - `geo:hasCentroid` – Extracts the centroid of the province polygons.
 - `geo:asWKT` – Retrieves the site geometries in WKT.
 - `geof:distance` – Calculates distances between province centroids and historical sites.
-

Query development

1. Retrieves provinces in Cambodia by defining `osmkey:boundary "administrative"` and `osmkey:admin_level 4` as the pattern.
 2. Extracts province centroids using `geo:hasCentroid` and gets their geometries with `geo:asWKT`.
 3. Filters the results that have `?isoCode` as KH- prefixes only.
 4. Gets attraction/historical sites using `osmkey:historic` and their spatial representations together with their geometries using `geo:hasGeometry` and `geo:asWKT` respectively.
 5. Computes the distances between each province centroid to the sites'.
 6. Filters the distances less than 50km.
 7. Sets `?en` for `?provinceName` instead of `?name` if either exists.
 8. Aggregates the provinces using `GROUP BY ?provinceName` followed by `?isoCode`.
 9. Sorts the results by the count of historical sites of each province in descending order.
-

Listing: Query for Use Case #3

```

SELECT ?provinceName ?isoCode (COUNT(?attraction) AS ?attractionCount)
WHERE {
  # Get provinces
  ?province osmkey:boundary "administrative" ;
            osmkey:admin_level 4 ;
            osmkey:name ?name ;
            osmkey:name:en ?en ;
            osmkey:IS03166-2 ?isoCode ;
            geo:hasCentroid ?provinceCentroid .
  ?provinceCentroid geo:asWKT ?provinceCentroidWKT .
  FILTER(REGEX(STR(?isoCode), "^KH-")) # Filters only Cambodian provinces

  # Get historical sites
  ?attraction osmkey:historic ?type ;
             geo:hasGeometry ?attrGeom .
  ?attrGeom geo:asWKT ?attractionWKT .

  # Compute distance from province centroid to attraction
  BIND(geof:distance(?provinceCentroidWKT, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre) AS
?distance)
  # Ensure the attraction is within a reasonable distance for counting
  FILTER(?distance < 50000)
  # English name PREFERRED if either exists

```

```

    OPTIONAL { BIND(COALESCE(?en, ?name) AS ?provinceName) }
  }
GROUP BY ?provinceName ?isoCode
ORDER BY DESC(?attractionCount)

```

Expected results

A list of provinces with their names, ISO codes, and the count of historical sites for each province.

3.5.2.4. Use Case # 4

Objective

Finds the cafes that are within or intersect the Russian market by defining the bounding box to the market's coordinates and verifying that the cafes are actually within or intersect the bounding box.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geo:wktLiteral` – Serializes the geometries to WKT format.
 - `geof:sfWithin` – Checks if the coffee shops are within the bounding box of the market.
 - `geof:sfIntersects` – Checks if the coffee shops intersect with the bonding box defined for the market.
-

Query development

1. Defines a bounding box of 750m for Russian Market using `BIND` and `geo:wktLiteral`.
 2. Retrieves coffee shop and their OBB geometry using `osmkey:amenity` with `osm2rdfgeom:obb`.
 3. Optionally gets the coffee names.
 4. Converts the OBB geometries to WKT using `geo:wktLiteral`.
 5. Filters the shops that are within the bounding box.
 6. Filters the shops that intersect with the bounding box.
-

Listing: Query for Use Case #4

```

# get coffee shops within or intersects with Russian Market Phnom Penh of 750m
SELECT ?cafe ?cafeName ?coffeeShopPoint
WHERE {
  # Define the 750m Bounding Box Around Russian Market
  BIND("POLYGON((104.9072 11.5338, 104.9072 11.5472, 104.9222 11.5472,
104.9222 11.5338, 104.9072 11.5338))"^^geo:wktLiteral AS ?ttpMarket)

```

```

# manually define the coffee shop's point - La'r Cafe
# BIND("POINT(104.9146614 11.5401775)"^^geo:wktLiteral AS ?coffeeShopPoint)

# Get coffee shops
?cafe osmkey:amenity "cafe" ;
    osm2rdfgeom:obb ?obb . # Extract OBB geometry

OPTIONAL { ?cafe osmkey:name ?cafeName}

# Convert OBB to WKT
BIND(REPLACE(STR(?obb), "POLYGON\\(\\(\\([^\ ]+) ([^\ ]+)\\)\\)", "POINT($1
$2)") AS ?pointWKT)
BIND(STRDT(?pointWKT, geo:wktLiteral) AS ?coffeeShopPoint)

# filter the shops within the bounding box
FILTER(geof:sfWithin(?coffeeShopPoint, ?ttpMarket))

# filter the shops intersect with the bounding box
FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?coffeeShopPoint, ?ttpMarket))
}

```

Expected results

A list of coffee shops, their names, and their coordinates.

3.5.2.5. Use Case # 5

Objective

Retrieves the research stations or institutes and their geometries by combining multiple conditions of searching for the stations.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geo:hasGeometry` – Gets the stations geometry representation.
 - `geo:hasCentroid` – Gets the station centroids.
 - `geo:asWKT` – Gets the station geometries in WKT format.
-

Query development

1. Retrieves the stations by combining the patterns of triples with `osmkey:research`, with `osmkey:amenity` having "research_institute" as object and triples with `osmkey:office`.
-

2. Retrieves station geometries and centroids in WKT formats using `geo:hasGeometry`, and `geo:hasCentroid` with `geo:asWKT` values.
3. Obtains station names as `?name` and English names as `?name_en` if exist.
4. Sets `?name` as the value if `?name_en` also exists for `?stationName`.
5. Order by the station names in ascending order.

Listing: Query for Use Case #5

```

SELECT ?station ?stationName ?stationCentroidWKT
WHERE {
  { ?station osmkey:research ?type . }
  UNION
  { ?station osmkey:amenity "research_institute" . }
  UNION
  { ?station osmkey:office ?type . }

  ?station geo:hasGeometry ?stationGeom .
  ?stationGeom geo:asWKT ?stationWKT .
  ?station geo:hasCentroid ?stationCentroid .
  ?stationCentroid geo:asWKT ?stationCentroidWKT .

  OPTIONAL { ?station osmkey:name ?name}
  OPTIONAL { ?station osmkey:name:en ?name_en}
  OPTIONAL {
    BIND(COALESCE(?name, ?name_en) AS ?stationName)
  }
}
ORDER BY ?stationName

```

Expected results

A list of stations, their names and their centroids.

3.5.2.6. Use Case # 6

Objective

Retrieves the research stations or institutes and their geometries and the nearest volcanoes by calculating the distances between the institute centroids and the volcanoes and filtering those that are less than 1 km.

GeoSPARQL functions and properties

- `geof:distance` – Calculates distance between the stations and the volcanoes.
 - `geo:hasGeometry` – Gets station geometries representation.
 - `geo:asWKT` – Gets station geometries stored in WKT format.
 - `geo:hasCentroid` – Gets station centroids.
-

Query development

1. Retrieves the stations by combining the patterns of triples with `osmkey:research`, with `osmkey:amenity` having "research_institute" as object and triples with `osmkey:office`.
 2. Retrieves station geometries and centroids in WKT formats using `geo:hasGeometry`, and `geo:hasCentroid` with `geo:asWKT` values.
 3. Optionally gets station names with `osmkey:name` if they exist.
 4. Retrieves volcanoes with `osmkey:natural` "volcano" and their geometries `geo:hasGeometry` with `geo:asWKT`.
 5. Optionally gets volcano names and statuses with `osmkey:name` and `osmkey:volcano:status` as `?volcanoName` and `?status`.
 6. Calculates the distance between station and volcano centroids using `geof:distance` in metre unit and filters the stations that have volcanoes less than 1km away.
 7. Order by volcano names in ascending order.
-

Listing: Query for Use Case #6

```

SELECT distinct
  ?station ?stationName ?stationCentroidWKT ?volcano ?volcanoName ?status
  ?volcanoWKT
  (geof:distance(?stationCentroidWKT, ?volcanoWKT, uom:metre) AS ?distance)
WHERE {
  # Get stations
  {
    ?station osmkey:research ?value .
  } UNION {
    ?station osmkey:amenity "research_institute" .
  } UNION {
    ?station osmkey:office ?value .
  }

  ?station geo:hasGeometry ?stationGeom .
  ?stationGeom geo:asWKT ?stationWKT .

```

```

# Get station centroids
?station geo:hasCentroid ?stationCentroid .
?stationCentroid geo:asWKT ?stationCentroidWKT .
OPTIONAL { ?station osmkey:name ?stationName }

# Get volcanoes
?volcano osmkey:natural "volcano";
           geo:hasGeometry ?geom .
?geom geo:asWKT ?volcanoWKT .

OPTIONAL { ?volcano osmkey:name ?volcanoName }
OPTIONAL { ?volcano osmkey:volcano:status ?status }
FILTER(geof:distance(?stationCentroidWKT, ?volcanoWKT, uom:metre) < 1000)
}
ORDER BY ?volcanoName
LIMIT 10

```

Expected results

A list of stations, their names, their centroids together with the nearest volcanoes, the distances between them and the volcano statuses.

3.6. Scenarios Development for GeoSPARQL Functionality Testing

In addition to the examples from Cambridgesemantics that were modified and used to test the functionality of GeoSPARQL functions on both Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB in section 3.4, scenarios in which different functions were utilized were also developed. These scenarios were used to further test the functionality of the implementations on one of actual datasets, the “Berlin” dataset. The experiment and the results of this functionality testing using the developed scenarios are presented in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 respectively. The listings that follow present the scenarios in question, along with the relevant functions utilized. The queries developed in this section will be included in the Attachments section.

Listing: Scenarios development list for Functionality Testing

#	Description	Functions Used
1	Get intersections of parks and rivers	geof:sfIntersects, geof:intersection
2	Get convexHull of parks and rivers and combine them	geof:convexHull, geof:union
3	Find parks without overlapping with rivers	geof:difference, geof:sfEquals

4	Get symmetrical differences of parks and rivers	geof:symDifference
5	Extract boundaries and envelopes	geof:boundary, geof:envelope
6	Check coordinate systems	geof:getSRID
7	Get roads touching but not crossing buildings	geof:ehMeet
8	Get coffee shops inside malls	geof:sfContains, geof:sfTouches, geof:sfCrosses
9	Find associated infrastructure that pass-through university campuses	geof:relate
10	Get parks not related to lakes	geof:sfDisjoint
11	Get parks that overlap with forests	geof:sfOverlaps
12	Get roads that disconnect or from hospital but within 100m	geof:rcc8dc, geof:rcc8eq

3.7. Benchmarking

Meanwhile, “HOBBIT”³², a benchmarking platform is chosen to perform Benchmarking process for the implementations. The platform was introduced in the paper [7] “Software for the GeoSPARQL compliance benchmark” where the author introduced the program and emphasized its importance of usage. The objective of benchmarking is to assess and compare the performance of Apache Jena Fuseki and GraphDB. To achieve this, three components must be taken into consideration: query execution time, indexing time, and resource consumption monitoring. In order to ensure the fairness of the evaluation, use case queries will be executed in the same hardware setup environment using the same available computational resources. In addition, the results of the query execution are derived from the execution of the queries multiple of times for each use case on each implementation. The total execution time for each use case is subsequently calculated and averaged for analyzing the caching effects of each implementation.

³² <https://hobbit-project.github.io/>

4. Experiments

This chapter presents a series of experiments conducted on both GeoSPARQL implementations, encompassing the initial phase of data loading and the subsequent benchmarking process. It is important to note that certain changes were made during the course of these experiments, and these modifications will be addressed throughout the subsequent sections. Ultimately, an experiment with an unplanned program, called “Qlever” will also be included, to showcase its potential and prospective contributions in GeoSPARQL implementation and support.

4.1. Hardware and Software

During the preparation and experimentation phases of the thesis, a local server environment was used, consistent throughout both stages. The hardware and software specifications of this environment are as follows:

Listing: Details of hardware and software setup environment

Chip	Apple M1 Pro	Software	Apache Jena Fuseki	GraphDB
Memory	16 GB	Version	5.2.0	10.8.3
OS	macOS Sonoma 14.5	License	Open Source	Freeware
Cores	8	Edition	Standalone	Standalone

4.2. Data Loading

First and foremost, the datasets were loaded into the chosen implementations of choice so that the experiment could commence. Indexing is the most important and crucial process in loading the datasets to the GeoSPARQL implementations. Both implementations provide both command-line and interface options for loading the data. Additionally, each system has its own parameters used for tweaking to fit the setup environment, such as `load`, along with `parallel` mode activation and `preload` provided by GraphDB, etc. While both systems offer the interface option for serving the purpose, during the experiments, however, indicated that GraphDB failed to index the triples properly for the Berlin dataset, which is the largest at over 20GB, without producing any warning or error messages, despite the fact that the `successfully imported` message was shown on the screen. The duration and the storage taken for indexing each dataset on each implementation will be presented and discussed in the following chapter.

4.2.1. Apache Jena Fuseki

In the case of Apache Jena Fuseki, the datasets were successfully loaded and indexed through the interface provided by the program itself when initiated with sufficient amount of heap size memory. Especially, for this particular experiment, customized amount of heap size was assigned when running the program before attempting to load the datasets; Berlin dataset, for instance, with a size greater than 20GB. The following command shows the command that

allocate 10GB of maximum heap size with `-Xmx10g` option when running the program, while the following figures after, show the steps onto creating and loading the datasets on Apache Jena Fuseki via the interface after the program has started.

Listing: Command for running Apache Jena Fuseki with 10GB of memory allocation

```
java -Xmx10g -cp "fuseki-server.jar:lib/*" org.apache.jena.fuseki.cmd.FusekiCmd
--config run/config.ttl --debug
```


Figure 7: Datasets manage page on Apache Jena Fuseki

On the interface, select `manage` and `new dataset` tab where name and type of dataset are expected. During the experiment, all datasets were created with `Persistent (TDB2)` mode to avoid getting the data erased after closing the program.

Figure 8: Add-data option on Apache Jena Fuseki

After creating the datasets, the data turtle files that were completely processed in Section 3.3, could be loaded with `add data` option in the existing `datasets` tab.

4.2.2. GraphDB

In addition to the previously mentioned possibility of indexing failure during the data importing process as outlined earlier, the Berlin dataset was only able to be loaded and indexed successfully using the `load` option with `parallel` mode enabled after multiple trials and errors. The following commands were used to load all the datasets into GraphDB:

Listing: Command for loading (indexing) Berlin dataset

```
→ graphdb-10.8.3 ./bin/importrdf load -f -i berlin -m parallel
/Users/macbookpro/Documents/ProITD/S3/Thesis/testing/osm2rdf/output/berlin-
latest-3.osm.ttl
```

Listing: Command for loading (indexing) Cambodia (khm) dataset

```
→ graphdb-10.8.3 ./bin/importrdf preload -f -i khm
/Users/macbookpro/Documents/ProITD/S3/Thesis/testing/osm2rdf/output/khm.osm.ttl
```

Listing: Command for loading (indexing) Antarctica (ata) dataset

```
→ graphdb-10.8.3 ./bin/importrdf load -f -i ata -m parallel
/Users/macbookpro/Documents/ProITD/S3/Thesis/testing/osm2rdf/output/ata.osm.ttl
```

4.2.3. Datasets Verification

To ensure that the datasets were correctly loaded and that geospatial data exist in the datasets and did not encounter any corruption during the importing process, the following two queries were used. The first query aims to find spatial entities (`?s`), retrieves their geometric representation (`?geo`) and ensure that geometry has a WKT representation (`geo:asWKT`) with limit of 100 and the second query is for retrieving the number of triples, subjects, predicates, and objects.

Listing: Retrieves entities with their geometries

```
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX osm2rdfgeom: <https://osm2rdf.cs.uni-freiburg.de/rdf/geom#>
SELECT ?s ?geo
WHERE {
  ?s geo:hasGeometry ?geo .
  ?geo geo:asWKT ?wkt .
```

```
}
LIMIT 100
```

Listing: Retrieves the number of triples, subjects, predicates and objects

```
SELECT
  (COUNT(*) AS ?tripleCount)
  (COUNT(DISTINCT ?s) AS ?subjectCount)
  (COUNT(DISTINCT ?p) AS ?predicateCount)
  (COUNT(DISTINCT ?o) AS ?objectCount)
WHERE {
  ?s ?p ?o .
}
```

Upon execution, it was clear that the datasets were indeed appropriately loaded when there were results returned and the following listing shows the statistics of the second query for giving a brief overview of the data.

Listing: Result of triple, subject, predicate and object counts

dataset	triple	subject	predicate	object
berlin	373691588	26172793	6005	55616175
khm	34921002	3368937	1494	9266212
ata	4419503	573736	994	1548862

4.3. Use Case Implementation in GraphDB

All the queries built previously in Section 3.5 were executed successfully on GraphDB with promisingly accurate results. For example, Q1 returned an expected list of 10 attractions ordered by its closest approximate distance to Galeria in Alexanderplatz.

	attraction	name_operator	type	distance
1	osm:node/4764023046	"Park Inn by Radisson Berlin Alexanderplatz"	"viewpoint"	"84.0"^^xsd:double
2	osm:way/417529567	"Urania-Weltzeituhr"	"attraction"	"175.0"^^xsd:double
3	osm:way/556435241	"Berliner Fernsehturm"	"attraction"	"220.0"^^xsd:double
4	osm:node/11812325269	"DeJa Vu Museum"	"museum"	"274.0"^^xsd:double
5	osm:node/3676215899	"Menschen Museum"	"museum"	"278.0"^^xsd:double
6	osm:node/6834779786	"Little Big City"	"museum"	"279.0"^^xsd:double
7	osm:node/12419975534	"Galerie Wasser"	"gallery"	"281.0"^^xsd:double
8	osm:way/474111581	"St. Marienkirche"	"attraction"	"329.0"^^xsd:double
9	osm:node/5875331486	"Illuseum Berlin"	"museum"	"339.0"^^xsd:double
10	osm:node/12357897312	"Lernort Keibelstraße"	"museum"	"395.0"^^xsd:double

Figure 9: Results of query execution for Q1 on GraphDB

The verification of the query was conducted by examining the third record/result obtained, which revealed that “Berliner Fernsehturm” was close to Galeria Alexanderplatz with a probable variance of approximately 150m (see Chapter 6 for limitations).

Figure 10: Direction from Galeria Alexanderplatz to Fernsehturm on OSM Maps

An additional of the verification of the accuracy of the results was conducted using the results returned in Q4 after query execution. In the list of the results below, “Ministry of Cat” coffee shop indicates that it is located within 750m of the Russian market’s bounding box.

cafe	cafeName	coffeeShopPoint
osm:node/3711763506	"Joma Bakery & Cafe"	"POINT(104.9154889 11.5390461)"
osm:node/4421518289		"POINT(104.9153211 11.5346927)"
osm:node/5814696453		"POINT(104.9078263 11.5467085)"
osm:node/6566851985		"POINT(104.9156998 11.5409855)"
osm:node/7216789180	"Ministry of Cat"	"POINT(104.91073 11.5408103)"
osm:node/4580583690		"POINT(104.9126353 11.5392603)"
osm:node/5940212936	"Starbucks"	"POINT(104.9155395 11.5371648)"
osm:node/6906265683	"Sacred Lotus Cafe and GuestHouse"	"POINT(104.9133097 11.5411267)"

Figure 11: Results of query execution for Q4 on GraphDB

Therefore, upon examination on the OSM Maps, it was determined that the coffee shop is, indeed, located at a proximity to the market that aligns with the resulted distance (see Chapter 6 for limitations).

Figure 12: Direction from Ministry of Cat to Russian Market on OSM Maps

4.4. Use Case Implementation in Apache Jena Fuseki

In Section 3.4, a difference in results returned for Apache Jena Fuseki when using `geof:distance` was also taken into consideration before executing the use case queries on the program. Upon executing the first query Q1 that utilized `geof:distance` function, failures showed. In this instance, the query did not generate any results.

/berlin3

```

SPARQL Query
To try out some SPARQL queries against the selected dataset, enter your query here.

Example Queries
Selection of triples Selection of classes

SPARQL Endpoint: /berlin3/
Content Type (SELECT): JSON
Content Type (GRAPH): Turtle

16 geo:nasueometry rgeom .
17 ?geom geo:asWKT ?attractionWKT .
18
19 OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:name ?attName }
20 OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:operator ?operator }
21
22 FILTER(?type IN("viewpoint", "museum", "zoo", "tower_viewer", "attraction", "gallery", "arts_center"))
23
24 BIND(round(geof:distance(?galeria, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre)) AS ?distance)
25 FILTER(?distance <=5000)
26 }
27 ORDER BY ?distance
28 LIMIT 10
29
Table Response 0 results in 0.486 seconds
Simple view Ellipse Filter query results Page size: 50

```

attraction	name_operator	type	distance
No data available in table			

Figure 13: No results returned for Q1 query on Apache Jena Fuseki

This outcome was unexpected as it contradicts the result in example 4 provided by GraphDB when the same function was also used and tested on the Apache Jena Fuseki shown in Section 3.4 although there was a variance in accuracy compared to the expected results. More importantly, `geof:distance` was included as a supported function in the compliance study introduced in Section 3.1. A more thorough examination revealed an interesting similarity between the GraphDB example dataset and the simplified dataset used in the compliance benchmarking study. Specifically, both documents were found to be in RDF format, with particular integrations section, and they both used the function with `geo:hasExactGeometry` property rather than the `geo:hasGeometry` property which typically found in OSM datasets as well as how the coordinates values are stored. The following listings illustrate the differences between the synthetic dataset utilized in the study and GraphDB sample dataset and predicates produced by OSM datasets.

Listing: Integrations section in RDF documents

```
<rdf:Property rdf:about="http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#hasExactGeometry">
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf
rdf:resource="http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry"/>
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf
rdf:resource="http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasDefaultGeometry"/>
</rdf:Property>

<rdf:Property rdf:about="http://example.org/ApplicationSchema#hasPointGeometry">
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf
rdf:resource="http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry"/>
</rdf:Property>
```

Listing: Sample coordinates stored in RDF documents

```
<geo:asWKT rdf:datatype="http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#wktLiteral">
  <![CDATA[
    <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84> Point(-83.4 34.3)
  ]]>
</geo:asWKT>
```

Listing: Sample coordinates stored in OSM dataset (ata.ttl)

```
osm2rdfgeom:osm_node_452093463 geo:asWKT "POINT(-63.4945578 -
64.8252567)"^^geo:wktLiteral .
```

While the exact cause of the observed failure remains uncertain when attempting to use the `geof:distance`, it is relevant to note the potential for the unexpected failures when utilizing different functions on an actual real-world data, particularly in the context of OSM datasets in turtle format.

Although not specified when and what the use cases are for, on Apache Jena Fuseki – geosparql documentation lists some filter functions for use. All the functions are available in the namespace <http://jena.apache.org/function/spatial#> using the `spatialF` prefix. One of the listed functions is `spatialF:distance`. An attempt was made to substitute this particular function in the queries built to evaluate its functionality. The query was executed successfully with this function substitution when trying out with the query for use case #1.

The screenshot shows the Apache Jena Fuseki SPARQL Query interface. The query is as follows:

```

17
18 OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:name ?attrName }
19 OPTIONAL { ?attraction osmkey:operator ?operator }
20
21 FILTER(?type IN("viewpoint", "museum", "zoo", "tower_viewer", "attraction", "gallery", "arts_center"))
22
23 # Use spatialF:distance to calculate distance
24 BIND(round(spatialF:distance(?galeria, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre)) AS ?distance)
25
26 # Filter for distances less than or equal to 5000 meters
27 FILTER(?distance <= 5000)
28 }
29 ORDER BY ?distance
30 LIMIT 10

```

The results table shows the following data:

attraction	name_operator	type	distance
1<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/47640...>	Park Inn by Radisson Berlin Alexanderplatz	viewpoint	"84.0e0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#doubl...
2<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/417529...>	Urania-Weltzeituhr	attraction	"175.0e0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#doubl...
3<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/556435...>	Berliner Fernsehturm	attraction	"220.0e0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#doubl...
4<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/118123...>	DeJa Vu Museum	museum	"273.0e0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#doubl...
5<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/36762...>	Menschen Museum	museum	"277.0e0"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#doubl...

Figure 14: Results returned for Q1 query after function substitution

As a result, changes were made to address this difference of functionality for Apache Jena Fuseki in queries where distance filtering is employed. The modifications to the queries are outlined in the following listings for each relevant case.

Listing: New prefix added for Apache Jena Fuseki

PREFIX `spatialF:` <<http://jena.apache.org/function/spatial#>>

Listing: Modified query for use case #1

original line

`BIND(round(geof:distance(?galeria, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre)) AS ?distance)`

new line

`BIND(round(spatialF:distance(?galeria, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre)) AS ?distance)`

Listing: Modified query for use case #2

```
# original line
BIND(geof:distance(?museumPoint, ?parkPoint, uom:metre) AS ?distance)
# new line
BIND(spatialF:distance(?museumPoint, ?parkPoint, uom:metre) AS ?distance)
```

Listing: Modified query for use case #3

```
# original line
BIND(geof:distance(?provinceCentroidWKT, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre) AS
?distance)
# new line
BIND(spatialF:distance(?provinceCentroidWKT, ?attractionWKT, uom:metre) AS
?distance)
```

Listing: Modified query for use case #6

```
# original line
FILTER(geof:distance(?stationCentroidWKT, ?volcanoWKT, uom:metre) < 1000)
# new line
FILTER(spatialF:distance(?stationCentroidWKT, ?volcanoWKT, uom:metre) < 1000)
```

4.5. Modified Benchmarking Approach

Following the experimental phase in both implementations in Section 4.3 and Section 4.4 previously, queries were modified to accommodate the differences in GeoSPARQL support regarding the functions and syntax in each implementation. Consequently, the HOBBIT platform which was introduced as the methodology method in Chapter 3 for benchmarking, was therefore dropped and substituted with Python based script to conduct the evaluation across implementations ensuring flexibility in queries execution. Despite the change of the tool, the methodology for benchmarking remains unchanged. All queries were executed on the same local server ten times, and the execution times were averaged to obtain a mean execution time for each use case on each implementation.

In Python, `SPARQLWrapper`³³ provides a simple wrapper to remotely execute SPARQL queries which fits exactly the benchmarking purpose without having to manually figure out the headers or other attributes when sending API requests. The library could be installed easily via `pip`, the Python packages manager. As the benchmarking process involves with transforming the data after sending API requests and visualizing the results afterwards, a few other libraries were also installed alongside `SPARQLWrapper` such as: `pandas`, `matplotlib` and `seaborn`. While the whole script of benchmarking using

³³ <https://sparqlwrapper.readthedocs.io/en/latest/main.html>

SPARQLWrapper and visualizing the result are enclosed in the Attachments page, the following command shows how a python environment was set up and installed the necessary mentioned libraries.

Listing: Setting up virtual environment for the benchmarking process

```
python3 -m venv venv # install a virtual environment called venv
source venv/bin/activate # activate the virtual environment
pip install SPARQLWrapper pandas matplotlib seaborn # install libraries
```

Once the virtual environment was completely set up and necessary libraries were installed, there was one additional thing needed to be done, the file containing the GeoSPARQL implementation details, SPARQL endpoints precisely, in order to make requests for queries execution. Initially, only JSON file was prepared with the engine and datasets/repositories info on each implementation as shown in the following listing.

Listing: Implementations config JSON file (lines truncated for readability)

```
{
  "jena_fuseki": {
    "endpoint": "http://localhost:3030",
    "repos": {
      "berlin3": {
        "queries": {
          "q1_jena": "",
          "q2_jena": ""
        }
      }
    },

    "graphdb": {
      "endpoint": "http://localhost:7200/repositories",
      "repos": {
        "berlin": {
          "queries": {
            "q1_graphdb": "",
            "q2_graphdb": ""
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

However, after making numerous attempts and although not specified on the documentation of the SPARQLWrapper library itself, the requests were only successfully made through the implementations when queries were sent as string literals. As a result, another separate Python file was developed to contain all the queries for the six use cases with variations in the function and syntax for each implementation as documented in Section 4.3 and Section 4.4. The following listing presents the simple Python file containing the queries with the variables

corresponding to those in the aforementioned config file. The results from this modified benchmarking process using the Python based script will be presented in the Chapter 5.

Listing: Python file containing all the queries (lines truncated for readability)

```
q1_jena = """
    PREFIX osmkey: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:>
    PREFIX spatialF: <http://jena.apache.org/function/spatial#>
    PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
    PREFIX uom: <http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/OGC/1.0/>

    # Top 10 places to visit starting with Galeria as the starting point

    SELECT ?attraction (COALESCE(?attrName, ?operator) AS ?name_operator)
    ?type ?distance
    """
```

4.6. Scenario-Based Query Testing and Execution

In section 3.6, a series of scenarios were introduced and developed to further assess the functionality of GeoSPARQL functions across both implementations. The majority of queries developed based on these scenarios were executed successfully on both platforms. However, two of functions, `geof:rcc8eq` and `geof:rcc8dc`, returned no results on Apache Jena Fuseki. This outcome is at contrary to the results obtained when these functions were utilized on the modified dataset from Cambridgesemantics. Additionally, in scenario 4, Apache Jena Fuseki failed to parse the JSON response onto the UI, likely due to validation constraints imposed on response length. The following figures illustrate some of the results obtained and verified through the use of WKT-GeoJSON converter³⁴, which facilitates the conversion of WKT values of the obtained geometries to GeoJSON format and their further visualization on `geojson.io`³⁵ site.

Figure 15: Apache Jena Fuseki failed to parse JSON response for scenario 4

³⁴ <https://geojson-to-wkt-converter.onrender.com/>

³⁵ <https://geojson.io/>

SPARQL Endpoint: /berlin3/ Content Type (SELECT): CSV Content Type (GRAPH): Turtle

```

4
5 SELECT ?park ?river
6   (geof:symDifference(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT) AS ?uniqueAreas)
7 WHERE {
8   ?park osmkey:leisure "park";
9        geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?parkWKT.
10
11  ?river osmkey:waterway "river";
12        geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?riverWKT.
13
14  # Ensure they intersect (for meaningful symDifference)
15  FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT))
16 }
17 LIMIT 10
    
```

7 results in 1.658 seconds

park	river	uniqueAreas
1https://w...	https://w...	GEOMETRYCOLLECTION(LINESTRING(13.576303 52.561312, 13.5777205 52.561102, 13.5780674 52.5610324, 13.5787731 52.5607463, 13.5790523 52.5606246, 13...
2https://w...	https://w...	GEOMETRYCOLLECTION(LINESTRING(13.5586437 52.5641008, 13.559983 52.564044), POLYGON((13.559983 52.564044, 13.5604183 52.5645696, 13.5606193 52...
3https://w...	https://w...	GEOMETRYCOLLECTION(LINESTRING(13.5603267 52.5640298, 13.5605904 52.5640245, 13.5608107 52.5640127, 13.5613349 52.5638349, 13.5615034 52.5637039...

Figure 16: Response successfully parsed in CSV format for scenario 4

geojson-to-wkt-converter.onrender.com

GeoJSON [Load example](#)

```

1 {
2   "type": "GeometryCollection",
3   "geometries": [
4     {
5       "type": "LineString",
6       "coordinates": [
7         [13.5603267, 52.5640298],
8         [13.5605904, 52.5640245],
9         [13.5608107, 52.5640127],
10        [13.5613349, 52.5638349],
11        [13.5615034, 52.5637039],
12        [13.5615876, 52.5634886],
13        [13.5616968, 52.5628698],
14      ]
15    }
16  ]
17 }
    
```

CLICK TO CONVERT

GeoJSON to WKT

WKT to GeoJSON

Copy to clipboard Save to file Draw on map

Well-Known-Text [Load example](#)

```

52.5548819, 13.5829429 52.5547451, 13.58325 52.5545386, 13.5833114
52.5544939, 13.5834174 52.5545218, 13.5833337 52.5546809,
13.5832165 52.5548735, 13.5832165 52.5549796, 13.5831271
52.5549991, 13.5829457 52.5549747, 13.5827671 52.5549294,
13.5827671 52.5548819), (13.5843131 52.5508842, 13.584442
52.5507887, 13.5844426 52.5506522, 13.5846248 52.5506365,
13.5852039 52.550567, 13.585312 52.5505723, 13.5853851 52.5505938,
13.5854309 52.5506371, 13.5854664 52.5506937, 13.5854735
52.5507283, 13.5854691 52.5507623, 13.585456 52.5507848,
13.5852669 52.5508996, 13.5849268 52.5510977, 13.5847067
52.5511193, 13.5846177 52.5511105, 13.5845246 52.5510939, 13.5844765
52.5510749, 13.5844295 52.5510382, 13.5843673 52.5509858,
13.584331 52.5509396, 13.5843131 52.5508842)))
    
```

Copy to clipboard Save to file Draw on map

Coloured Light Dark Drawing: WKT Toggle map size

Figure 17: Symdifferences of Eichepark and Neue Wuhle from scenario 4 rendered on geojson-to-wkt-converter.onrender.com

The screenshot shows the Apache Jena Fuseki query interface. The query is as follows:

```

7 SELECT ?hospital ?residential (spatialF:distance(?hwkt, ?rwkt, uom:metre) AS ?distance)
8 WHERE {
9   ?hospital osmkey:amenity "hospital";
10  geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?hwkt.
11  ?residential osmkey:highway "residential";
12  geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?rwkt.
13  FILTER(
14    geof:rcc8eq(?hwkt, ?rwkt) ||
15    geof:rcc8dc(?hwkt, ?rwkt)
16  )
17  FILTER(spatialF:distance(?hwkt, ?rwkt, uom:metre)<100)
18 }
19 order by desc(?hospital)
20 limit 5

```

Below the query editor, the interface shows a table with columns for 'hospital', 'residential', and 'distance'. The table is empty, with the message "No data available in table" displayed.

Figure 18: No results returned on Apache Jena Fuseki for scenario 12

The screenshot shows the geojson.io interface. On the left, a map of Berlin is displayed with a red box highlighting a specific area. The map shows the Berlin Jewish Hospital and the street Heinz-Galinski-Straße. A red box highlights a disconnection between the hospital and the street. On the right, the JSON representation of the highlighted area is shown:

```

9  "geometry": {
10    "type": "Polygon",
11    "coordinates": [
12      [
13        [13.3686182, 52.5547557],
14        [13.3710509, 52.5544494],
15        [13.3721085, 52.5560173],
16        [13.3720564, 52.5560298],
17        [13.3717417, 52.5561077],
18        [13.3716868, 52.5561216],
19        [13.3716938, 52.5561581],
20        [13.3706412, 52.5562441],
21        [13.3692345, 52.5563541],
22        [13.3689668, 52.5563747],
23        [13.3688903, 52.5560206],
24        [13.3688859, 52.5559987],
25        [13.3686182, 52.5547557]
26      ]
27    ]
28  },
29  {
30    "type": "Feature",
31    "properties": {
32      "name": "Road"
33    },
34    "geometry": {
35      "type": "LineString",
36      "coordinates": [ [13.3724758, 52.5565575], [
37      ]
38    ]
39  }
40 }

```

Figure 19: Jewish Hospital disconnected from Heinz-Galinski-Straße from scenario 12 visualized on geojson.io

4.7. Experiment with Qlever

In Chapter 3, osm2rdf was introduced as a tool for converting the dataset into a compatible working format with the GeoSPARQL implementations. The University of Freiburg actually also introduces their own SPARQL engine called “Qlever”³⁶. As stated on the documentation, it is also claimed to be extremely fast and able to efficiently index and query very large queries from knowledge graphs with over 100 billion triples on a single standard PC or server. Qlever also provides a demo site³⁷ where many knowledge graphs are hosted with given sample

³⁶ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever>

³⁷ <https://qlever.cs.uni-freiburg.de/wikidata>

SPARQL queries for different use cases. After going through the demo site and seeing how fast, convenient and effective the engine is, during the experiments phase, Qlever was also tried out to see if it also supports GeoSPARQL since it is also on the list of notified contributors for GeoSPARQL updates on Github. The easiest way to install qlever is using `pip`, the package manager for Python. It is also important to note that `docker` and `docker demon` are required throughout the process.

Listing: Command for installing qlever

```
pip install qlever
```

After the installation, several commands and options are available for use for setting up the data repositories, starting/stopping the server and accessing the UI, etc. The commands are as followed:

Commands List

<code>qlever setup-config olympics</code>	<code># Get Qleverfile (config file) for this dataset</code>
<code>qlever get-data</code>	<code># Download the dataset</code>
<code>qlever index</code>	<code># Build index data structures for this dataset</code>
<code>qlever start</code>	<code># Start a QLever server using that index</code>
<code>qlever example-queries</code>	<code># Launch some example queries</code>
<code>qlever ui</code>	<code># Launch the QLever UI</code>

There are several configuration templates available³⁸ which could be chosen from based on actual needs. In fact, it is even greater that the actual qlever project which is referred to as `qlever-control`, equivalent to `pip install qlever` could also be cloned for modification and further development with the following steps:

Steps to cloning and developing qlever-control

```
git clone https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever-control
cd qlever-control
pip install -e .
```

`vvz` Qleverfile template was chosen for setting up Berlin dataset on the engine with the “`qlever setup-config vvz`” command as the configuration parameters in the template file were the closest to the actual local machine environment. However, due to the limited computational resources, some changes were made and adjusted until the successful attempt at indexing the dataset. The following shows the final Qleverfile that successfully managed to index the dataset.

Qleverfile for Berlin dataset (lines truncated for readability)

³⁸ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever-control/tree/main/src/qlever/Qleverfiles>

```
[data]
NAME          = berlin
[index]
INPUT_FILES   = berlin-latest.osm.rdf.bz2
CAT_INPUT_FILES = bzcat ${INPUT_FILES}
PARSER_BUFFER_SIZE = 50M
STXXL_MEMORY  = 2G
SETTINGS_JSON = { "ascii-prefixes-only": false, "num-triples-per-batch": 50000
}
[server]
MEMORY_FOR_QUERIES = 12G
[ui]
UI_CONFIG = olympics
UI_PORT   = 8180
```

The most important section `index` where necessary adjustments were made and could be done depending on the server specifications. Additionally, on `UI_CONFIG` line, only `olympics` could be used. Otherwise, the program was not running properly. It is unknown whether this was a bug. Once the Qleverfile is ready, `qllever get-data` was used to prepare for dataset retrieval which is located locally in this case, and export the settings properties to json file for indexing process. Next, indexing process started with `qllever index` command. During the indexing process which is usually the most time-consuming process in loading the RDF documents, an index text log file was also produced alongside the command line prompt which is helpful for debugging and monitoring the process. The following shows the result from the index log file. It is noticeable that the indexing process took approximately 20 minutes for Berlin dataset which is more than 20 GB in size which is the fastest among the chosen GeoSPARQL implementations.

Index log file (lines truncated for readability)

```
2025-03-08 13:12:19.384 - INFO: [1mQLever IndexBuilder, compiled on Sat Feb 22
02:04:18 UTC 2025 using git hash 8fe064[22m
2025-03-08 13:12:19.392 - INFO: You specified "num-triples-per-batch = 50,000",
choose a lower value if the index builder runs out of memory
2025-03-08 13:31:34.612 - INFO: Statistics for PSO: #relations = 5,999, #blocks
= 12,014, #triples = 373,720,412
2025-03-08 13:31:35.406 - INFO: Index build completed
```

Once the dataset was completely and successfully indexed, `qllever start` and `qllever ui` commands were used to start the server and launch the UI workbench. Once the UI started, testing with GeoSPARQL queries on Qlever could be done. The following figure shows the results of testing a sample query provided by Qlever for listing all German cities.

Query results: 2,098 lines found 1,195ms in total 1,193ms for computation 2ms for resolving and sending

Limited to 100 results; show all 2,098 results

	?name	?population
1	Berlin	3,782,202
2	Hamburg	1,910,160
3	München	1,510,378

Figure 20: Listing all German cities on Qlever

However, when tested with the actual GeoSPARQL functions such as `geof:buffer` and `geof:distance`, errors were returned. The following figures show the errors when testing both functions. In the case of `geof:buffer`, the error message indicated that the function is not currently supported. This error would be very informative in the development and debugging processes if GeoSPARQL were supported.

Error processing query

Not supported: Function "<http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/buffer>" is currently not supported by QLever.

Your query was:

```
PREFIX geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
PREFIX uom: <http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/OGC/1.0/>
SELECT (geof:buffer(?x,?y,?z) as ?buffer)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y ?z) {
    ('Point (0 0)' 2 uom:meter)
    ('POLYGON ((1 1, 1 4, 4 4, 4 1))'^^geo:wktLiteral 20 uom:millimeter)
  }
}
```

Figure 21: Error message for `geof:buffer` on Qlever

On the other hand, the error provided when trying to use `geof:distance` is misleading and appears to be inaccurate, despite the syntax and query structure being correct.

Error processing query

Invalid SPARQL query: Function `geof:distance` takes two arguments

Your query was:

```
PREFIX geof: <http://www.opengis.net/def/function/geosparql/>
PREFIX uom: <http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/OGC/1.0/>
SELECT (geof:distance(?x,?y,?z) as ?distance)
WHERE {
  VALUES (?x ?y ?z) {
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (0 0)' '<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (3 4)' uom:millimeter)
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (0 0)' '<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (3 4)' uom:kilometer)
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (0 0)' '<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (3 4)' uom:metre)
    ('<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (0 0)' '<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>Point (3 4)' uom:foot)
  }
}
```

Figure 22: Error message for `geof:distance` on Qlever

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Functionality Testing

The results of the functionality testing on GeoSPARQL functions using static example queries with modifications (see section 3.4) indicate that GraphDB supported a greater number of functions than Apache Jena Fuseki when tested on a different dataset than the one provided by either of the implementation, as well as the one found in on compliance and benchmarking studies³⁹. Some of the functions below from the list were used when building the queries for use case development (see section 3.5). It is particularly interesting to note that `geof:distance` does not appear to be supported in Apache Jena Fuseki, as indicated by the list, that aligns with the functionality of the function when executing the queries in the specified use cases (see section 4.4 for further details).

Listing: Result of Functionality Testing using static example queries

Type	Function	Jena Fuseki	GraphDB
Non-Topological	<code>geof:distance</code>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:buffer</code>		
Non-Topological	<code>geof:convexHull</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:intersection</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:union</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:difference</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:symDifference</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:envelope</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:boundary</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>geof:getSRID</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	<code>Geof:relate</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfEquals</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfDisjoint</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfIntersects</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfTouches</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfCrosses</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfWithin</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfContains</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	<code>geof:sfOverlaps</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	<code>geof:ehEquals</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	<code>geof:ehDisjoint</code>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	<code>geof:ehMeet</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	<code>geof:ehOverlap</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	<code>geof:ehCovers</code>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

³⁹ https://github.com/OpenLinkSoftware/GeoSPARQLBenchmark/tree/master/src/main/resources/gsb_dataset

Egenhofer	geof:ehCoveredBy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	geof:ehInside		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	geof:ehContains		
RCC8	geof:rcc8eq	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8dc	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8ec		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8po		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8tpp		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8tppi		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8ntpp		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8ntppi		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Meanwhile, the results from conducting functionality testing on the “Berlin” dataset where the experiments of execution on scenario-based queries were detailed in section 4.6 suggest that approximately, 65% of the functions out of the 35 functions in the previous listing were tested and resulted to match with results from testing on the static sample queries with the exception of two functions `geof:rcc8eq` and `geof:rcc8dc` used in scenario number 12.

Listing: Result of Functionality Testing using static example queries

Type	Function	Jena Fuseki	GraphDB
Non-Topological	geof:distance		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:buffer		
Non-Topological	geof:convexHull	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:intersection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:union	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:difference	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:symDifference	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:envelope	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:boundary	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:getSRID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Non-Topological	geof:relate	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfEquals	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfDisjoint	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfIntersects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfTouches	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfCrosses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfWithin	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfContains	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Simple Feature	geof:sfOverlaps	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Egenhofer	geof:ehMeet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

RCC8	geof:rcc8eq	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
RCC8	geof:rcc8dc	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.2. Benchmarking

One of the components for the benchmarking process outlined in the objectives section in chapter 1 is indexing time, defined as the duration and space required for each dataset to be imported and loaded onto the repositories and datasets of both platforms. The following list illustrates that Apache Jena Fuseki generally takes less time to import and index small and mid-sized datasets. However, it took nearly twice as much time to index the “Berlin” dataset. Additionally, it requires more storage space for indexed directories.

Listing: Result of benchmarking indexing time

Dataset	Indexing Duration		Storage Taken	
	Jena	GraphDB	Jena	GraphDB
ata	2mn	7mn21s	1.06 GB	792.9 MB
khm	5mn	10mn	5.6 GB	3.31 GB
berlin	4hr50m	2hr48m	49.83 GB	34.81 GB

Furthermore, the results of the benchmarking on the use case queries execution using a Python-based script demonstrate that both implementations returned the same number of results for all the use cases, with the execution time varying for each case between the two. Apache Jena Fuseki outperformed GraphDB in five out of the six use cases, with the time reduction ranging from approximately 40% to more than 150% in milliseconds.

Listing: Result of benchmarking the use cases execution

Use Case	Returned Results		Execution Time (ms)		Difference in %
	Jena	GraphDB	Jena	GraphDB	
Q1	10	10	83.9	219.54	161.67%
Q2	10	10	3723.55	5336.51	43.32%
Q3	25	25	263	510.34	94.05%
Q4	67	67	61.44	126.01	105.09%
Q5	137	137	14.06	36.54	159.89%
Q6	10	10	43.31	27.87	-35.65%

The following graph is presented to highlight the execution time differences clearly. It indicates that, in general, both implementations required less than one second to execute the queries, with the exception of Q2, where it took the longest to execute for both implementations.

Figure 23: Graph showing GeoSPARQL Use Case Execution Time Comparison on both implementations

6. Limitations

The experiments in this thesis were conducted with limited and relatively small computational resources, with both limited free disk space and memory as detailed in Chapter 4. Therefore, the datasets obtained for the experiments were rather limited and not as broad in terms of geospatial data availability.

Furthermore, the experiments did not prioritize the distance precision of the results retrieval due to the utilization of diverse methodologies in terms of GeoSPARQL implementation functionality and OSM route calculation. The primary objective was to assess and evaluate the practical functionality of GeoSPARQL implementation, particularly in the context of real-world data, specially OSM data.

Lastly, the benchmarking process was not executed on the standardized benchmarking platform as proposed in Chapter 3; thus, the computational resources consumption during the queries execution for the use cases were not logged.

7. Conclusion

In the course of the conducted experiments, it was revealed that Apache Jena Fuseki appeared to be anticipating a certain specific format and structure for the datasets. This led to engine's inability to support certain functions. Meanwhile, GraphDB demonstrated a straightforward approach in its support for GeoSPARQL, particularly in the context of real-world datasets. Both systems were found to compliment each other in terms of performance and storage strategies. Specifically, Apache Jena Fuseki demonstrated the potential to perform better in indexing, while GraphDB requires less storage space for its indexed directories.

Therefore, a comparative analysis of the two GeoSPARQL implementations concludes that both offer comparable support for GeoSPARQL. However, a closer examination throughout the experiments phase indicates that while Apache Jena Fuseki's biggest strength is its execution time, GraphDB exhibits certain advantages, particularly in terms of user control on the interface workbench, configuration flexibility, comprehensive documentation, and informative query execution messages.

Furthermore, in contrast to Apache Jena Fuseki, an open-sourced project, GraphDB, developed and supported by Ontotext, offers a free version in addition to an enterprise license; thus, the continued availability of the free version is not guaranteed. Nevertheless, in the event that Apache Jena Fuseki provides enhanced and more extensive GeoSPARQL support in the future, GraphDB remains a valuable tool for development, given the comprehensive features offered by GraphDB itself.

Attachments

Listing: Python script used for benchmarking use cases query execution

```
import json
import time
import pandas as pd

from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
from datetime import datetime

now = datetime.now()
dt_string = now.strftime("%d%m%Y_%H%M")
endpoints = []
n_times = 10

def read_config(file: json):
    with open(file, 'r') as f:
        config = json.load(f)
    return config

def query_data(endpoint, query_name, query):

    sparql = SPARQLWrapper(
        f"{endpoint}"
    )

    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    sparql.setQuery(query)

    try:
        start_time = time.time()
        ret = sparql.queryAndConvert()
        no_results = len(ret["results"]["bindings"])

        if no_results > 0:
            end_time = time.time()
            execution_time = (end_time - start_time) * 1000 # to milliseconds
            results.append((endpoint, query_name, no_results, execution_time))
    return no_results
```

```
except Exception as e:
    print(e)

def structure_endpoint(config):
    import queries

    """Iterate over engines and repositories to execute queries."""
    for engine, engine_config in config.items():
        engine_endpoint = engine_config.get("endpoint", "n/a")

        # Ensure "repos" exists in engine_config
        if "repos" not in engine_config:
            print(f"Warning: No 'repos' found for {engine}")
            continue

        for repo_name, repo_data in engine_config["repos"].items():
            if engine == "jena_fuseki":
                endpoint = f"{engine_endpoint}/{repo_name}/sparql"
            else:
                endpoint = f"{engine_endpoint}/{repo_name}"

            if "queries" not in repo_data:
                print(f"Warning: No 'queries' found for repo {repo_name}")
                continue

            for query_name, query_string in repo_data["queries"].items():
                query_string = getattr(queries, query_name, None)
                if query_string:
                    endpoints.append((endpoint, query_name, query_string))
                else:
                    print(f"Query: {query_name} not found in queries.py")

    return endpoints

if __name__ == '__main__':
    results = []
    config = None

    json_config = read_config("./config.json")
    endpoints_result = structure_endpoint(json_config)

    for n in range(n_times):
```

```
print("n: ", n)
for query_endpoint in endpoints:
    endpoint = query_endpoint[0]
    query_name = query_endpoint[1]
    query_string = query_endpoint[2]
    print(f"Running query '{query_name}' on {endpoint}...")
    result = query_data(endpoint, query_name, query_string)
    print(f"Returned Results: {result}")

if results:
    df = pd.DataFrame(results, columns=["Implementation", "Use Case",
    "Results", "Execution Time (ms)"])
    df = df.groupby(['Implementation', 'Use Case', 'Results'],
    as_index=False).agg({'Execution Time (ms)': 'sum'})\
        .sort_values(['Implementation', 'Use Case'])
    df['Execution Time (ms)'] = df['Execution Time (ms)']/n_times
    df.to_csv(f"benchmarks_result_{dt_string}.csv", index=False)
```

Listing: Python script used for transforming and visualizing the benchmark results

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

def transform_results(csv):
    df = pd.read_csv(csv)

    # transform Implementation column values
    df["Implementation"] = df["Implementation"].map(lambda x: "Apache Jena
Fuseki" if "3030" in x else "GraphDB")
    # transform use case column values
    df["Use Case"] = df["Use Case"].map(lambda x: x.replace("_jena", "") if
"_jena" in x else x.replace("_graphdb", "")).astype('str')
    # transform execution time
    df["Execution Time (ms)"] = round(df["Execution Time (ms)"],2)

    df.to_csv(f"transformed_benchmarked_results_{csv}.csv")
    return df

def visualize(df, file_name):
    df = df.sort_values(['Implementation', 'Use Case'])
    df["Use Case"] = df["Use Case"].astype(str)

    plt.figure(figsize=(10, 5))
    sns.lineplot(data=df, x="Use Case", y="Execution Time (ms)",
hue="Implementation", marker="o")
    plt.title("GeoSPARQL Use Case Execution Time Comparison")
    plt.xticks(rotation=45)

    for implementation in df["Implementation"].unique():
        subset = df[df["Implementation"] == implementation]

        max_index = subset["Execution Time (ms)"].idxmax()
        max_row = subset.loc[max_index]

        peak_x = max_row["Use Case"]
        peak_y = max_row["Execution Time (ms)"]

        print(f"Implementation: {implementation}, Peak: {peak_x}, {peak_y}")
```

```
plt.annotate(
    f"{peak_y:.2f} ms",
    (peak_x, peak_y),
    textcoords="offset points",
    xytext=(0, 10),
    ha='center',
    fontsize=10,
    color="black",
    weight="bold"
)

plt.savefig(f"query_execution_comparison_{file_name}.png", dpi=350,
bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()

def pivot_results(df, file_name):
    new_df = df.pivot(index="Use Case", columns=["Implementation"],
values=["Results", "Execution Time (ms)"]).sort_values(['Use Case'])
    new_df.to_csv(f"benchmarks_{file_name}.csv")

file_name = "benchmarks_result_26032025804.csv"
df = transform_results(file_name)
pivot_results(df, file_name)
visualize(df, file_name)
```

Listing: Query for scenario 1

```

SELECT ?park ?parkName ?river ?riverName ?intersection
WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?parkGeo .
  ?parkGeo geo:asWKT ?parkWKT .
  OPTIONAL{?park osmkey:name ?parkName}
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?riverGeo .
  ?riverGeo geo:asWKT ?riverWKT .
  OPTIONAL{?river osmkey:name ?riverName}
  FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT))
  BIND(geof:intersection(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT) AS ?intersection)
}
order by ?intersection

```

Listing: Query for scenario 2

```

SELECT ?park ?river
      (geof:convexHull(?parkWKT) AS ?parkHull)
      (geof:convexHull(?riverWKT) AS ?riverHull)
      (geof:union(geof:convexHull(?parkWKT), geof:convexHull(?riverWKT)) AS
?combinedHull)
WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?parkGeo .
  ?parkGeo geo:asWKT ?parkWKT .
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?riverGeo .
  ?riverGeo geo:asWKT ?riverWKT .
  FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT))

```

Listing: Query for scenario 3

```

SELECT ?park ?parkName ?river ?riverName
      (geof:difference(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT) AS ?parkWithoutRiver)
WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?parkGeo .
  ?parkGeo geo:asWKT ?parkWKT .
  OPTIONAL {?park osmkey:name ?parkName}
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river" ;

```

```

    geo:hasGeometry ?riverGeo .
  ?riverGeo geo:asWKT ?riverWKT .
  OPTIONAL {?river osmkey:name ?riverName}
  FILTER(!STRSTARTS(STR(?parkWKT), "GEOMETRYCOLLECTION"))
  FILTER(!STRSTARTS(STR(?riverWKT), "GEOMETRYCOLLECTION"))
  FILTER(!geof:sfEquals(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT))
}

```

Listing: Query for scenario 4

```

SELECT ?park ?parkName ?river ?riverName
      (geof:symDifference(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT) AS ?uniqueAreas)
WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park";
      geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?parkWKT.
  OPTIONAL {?park osmkey:name ?parkName}
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river";
      geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?riverWKT.
  OPTIONAL {?river osmkey:name ?riverName}
  FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?parkWKT, ?riverWKT))
}
LIMIT 10

```

Listing: Query for scenario 5

```

SELECT ?river
      (geof:boundary(?riverWKT) AS ?riverBoundary)
      (geof:envelope(?riverWKT) AS ?riverBoundingBox)
WHERE {
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river" ;
      geo:hasGeometry [ geo:asWKT ?riverWKT ].
  FILTER(!STRSTARTS(STR(?riverWKT), "GEOMETRYCOLLECTION"))
}

```

Listing: Query for scenario 6

```

SELECT ?river (geof:getSRID(?wkt) AS ?srid)
WHERE {
  ?river osmkey:waterway "river"; geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?wkt.
  FILTER(geof:getSRID(?wkt) != "EPSG:4326"^^xsd:string)
}
LIMIT 5

```

Listing: Query for scenario 7

```

SELECT ?road ?building
WHERE {
  ?road osmkey:highway []; geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?rWKT.
  ?building osmkey:building []; geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?bWKT.
  FILTER(geof:ehMeet(?rWKT, ?bWKT))
}

```

Listing: Query for scenario 8

```

SELECT ?mall ?mallName ?amenity ?amenityName
  (geof:sfContains(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT) AS ?contains)
  (geof:sfTouches(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT) AS ?touches)
  (geof:sfCrosses(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT) AS ?crosses)
  ?mallWKT ?amenityWKT
WHERE {
  ?mall osmkey:shop "mall" ;
    osmkey:name ?mallName ;
    geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?mallWKT .
  ?amenity osmkey:amenity "cafe" ;
    osmkey:name ?amenityName ;
    geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?amenityWKT .
  FILTER(
    geof:sfContains(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT) ||
    geof:sfTouches(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT) ||
    geof:sfCrosses(?mallWKT, ?amenityWKT)
  )
}
LIMIT 10

```

Listing: Query for scenario 9

```

SELECT ?university ?universityName ?road ?roadName
  (geof:relate(?buildingWKT, ?roadWKT, "T*F**FFF*") AS ?relate)
WHERE {
  ?university osmkey:amenity "university";
    geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?buildingWKT.
  OPTIONAL {?university osmkey:name ?universityName}
  ?road osmkey:highway ?roadType;
    geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?roadWKT.
  OPTIONAL {?road osmkey:name ?roadName}
  FILTER(geof:sfIntersects(?buildingWKT, ?roadWKT))
}
LIMIT 5

```

Listing: Query for scenario 10

```

SELECT ?park ?parkName ?lake
WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park";
        geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?parkWKT.
  OPTIONAL {?park osmkey:name ?parkName}
  ?lake osmkey:water "lake" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?lakeGeo .
  ?lakeGeo geo:asWKT ?lakeWKT .
  FILTER(geof:sfDisjoint(?parkWKT, ?lakeWKT))
}
LIMIT 5

```

Listing: Query for scenario 11

```

SELECT ?park ?forest WHERE {
  ?park osmkey:leisure "park" ;
        geo:hasGeometry ?parkGeo .
  ?parkGeo geo:asWKT ?parkWKT .

  ?forest osmkey:landuse "forest" ;
          geo:hasGeometry ?forestGeo .
  ?forestGeo geo:asWKT ?forestWKT .

  FILTER(geof:sfOverlaps(?parkWKT, ?forestWKT))
}
LIMIT 5

```

Listing: Query for scenario 12

```

SELECT ?hospital ?residential
(geof:rcc8dc(?hWKT, ?rWKT) AS ?is_disconnected)
(geof:rcc8eq(?hWKT, ?rWKT) AS ?is_equal)
WHERE {
  ?hospital osmkey:amenity "hospital";
            geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?hWKT.
  ?residential osmkey:highway "residential";
              geo:hasGeometry/geo:asWKT ?rWKT.
  FILTER(geof:rcc8dc(?hWKT, ?rWKT)) || FILTER(geof:rcc8eq(?hWKT, ?rWKT))
  FILTER(geof:distance(?hWKT, ?rWKT, uom:metre) < 100)
}
LIMIT 5

```

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I herewith formally declare that I have written the submitted thesis independently in all parts. I did not use any outside support except for the quoted literature and other sources mentioned in the paper. I declare that the thesis has not been presented in the same or a similar form in any other examination. I clearly marked and separately listed all of the literature and all of the other sources which I employed when producing this academic work, either literally or in content.

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